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Lankatilaka Inscriptions

ON the rock to the south of the Buddhist shrine of Laṅkātilaka in the village of Rabbēgomuwa in Uḍunuvara, Kandy District, there are two extensive areas covered with deeply and carefully engraved writing. The upper stretch, comprising an area of 25 ft. 11 in. by 12 ft. 9 in., contains 40 lines of Sinhalese writing, of which 33 form an inscription dated in the reign of Bhuvanaikabāhu IV of Gaṁpaḷa ; the remainder is a record of his successor, Vikramabāhu III. The writing in the lower stretch, measuring 21 ft. by 16 ft. 11 in., is Tamil and runs into 46 lines. The letters in the Sinhalese record range in size between $2\frac{1}{2}$ in. and 3 in., and the average size of the Tamil letters is 3 in. About eighteen letters in line 5 and twelve letters in line 6 of the inscription of Vikramabāhu have become illegible due to the weathering of the rock. A letter or two have become blurred here and there in the other two inscriptions. Apart from these, the records are in an excellent state of preservation, and can be easily deciphered from the stone itself or from inked estampages.¹ The Sinhalese inscription of Bhuvanaikabāhu at Laṅkātilaka-vihāra has been included as No. 172 in the List of Inscriptions forming Appendix F in H. C. P. Bell's *Annual Report of the Archaeological Survey of Ceylon* for 1911-12 (p. 120) ; the Tamil inscription is No. 45 in the list of Tamil inscriptions in the same report (p. 115). The estampage of the left-hand portion of lines 1-21 of the inscription of Bhuvanaikabāhu has been reproduced, and a reading given of this fragment, by H. C. P. Bell in *JCBRAS.*, Vol. XXII (No. 65), pp. 360-362 and Plate C, in order to illustrate the development of writing during this period. No complete reading of the Laṅkātilaka inscriptions from the rock or an estampage has yet been published.

In Vol. X of *JCBRAS.*, (No. 34), pp. 83-95, Mudaliyar B. Gunasekara has published, as far back as 1887, what purports to be the text, transliteration and translation, with appended notes, of the Laṅkātilaka ins-

1. The statement made by Sir D.B. Jayatilaka (*Sāhityalipi*, Colombo, 1940, p. 120) that the letters in parts of the inscription of Bhuvanaikabāhu IV are so effaced as to be undecipherable is perhaps due to hearsay.

cription of Bhuvanaikabāhu IV, and it is this edition of the epigraph that has been utilised by subsequent writers on Ceylon history in their studies of the Gaṇpaḷa period.² Mudaliyar Gunasekara does not state the source from which he derived the text of the document; he makes no claim to have deciphered it from the rock. Apart from certain orthographical differences, the text, for about two-thirds of the document from its beginning, is in agreement with the writing on the rock, but towards the end, in the exhortations and imprecations, the text as published by Mudaliyar Gunasekara differs considerably from what is written on the rock, and contains many words and phrases as well as rhetorical flourishes not found in the document as it was engraved in the fourteenth century. On the other hand, certain phrases engraved on the stone are wanting in Mudaliyar Gunasekara's text.

In the Laṅkātilaka Temple are preserved four copper-plates, each measuring 1 ft. 3½ in. by 3 in., of which the first three are inscribed on both sides and the fourth is on one side only. The fourth plate bears grants of lands made to the shrine in the reigns of Rājādhirājasimha of Kandy and his predecessor, Kīrtisī Rājasimha. The texts of these eighteenth century documents are preceded by those of the inscriptions of Bhuvanaikabāhu IV and Vikramabāhu III. Where Mudaliyar Gunasekara's text (*Gt.*) differs from the document as it has been engraved on the stone, the text inscribed on the copper-plates (*Cpt.*) generally also does so; but the former does not appear to be based on the latter, for there are many instances of discrepancies between them. In some places, where Mudaliyar Gunasekara's text has an obviously corrupt reading, that on the copper-plates contains a more satisfactory one; for instance, Mudaliyar Gunasekara has the reading *savinjājīṭana* which in a note he corrects to *sainyapatīn* (p. 89), whereas the copper-plates read *sainya-janān*, which agrees with the text of the Tamil inscription, but not quite with that of the Sinhalese. In place of *ē-Senālaṅkādhikārīn* in *Cpt.*, *Gt.* has *Laṅkā-senevirat-maharajānan visin*. The script of the copper-plates is almost the same as the modern Sinhalese, and could be easily read by any person educated in Sinhalese. If Mudaliyar Gunasekara derived his text from these copper-plates, there is no reason why it should have differed from the *Cpt.* The conclusion thus ought to be that the Mudaliyar's text of this inscription has been based on a copy of it written on palm leaves. Several such copies appear to have been in existence, for among the Neville collection of manuscripts in the British Museum there is one such which shows arbitrary changes in readings, found neither on the rock, nor in the *Cpt.*, nor in *Gt.* For instance, the bare reference to

2. See Codrington, *A Short History of Ceylon*, Macmillan & Co., London, 1947, p. 88, and *Gampola Period of Ceylon History*, JCBRAS., Vol. XXXII, No. 86, pp. 265ff.

the Śaka era by the words *Śrī-Śakavarṣayen* on the rock as well as in *Gt.* and *Cpt.*, has been considered not impressive enough by the scribe who was responsible for this manuscript; he has amplified it into *Śrī sakalajyotiśśāstrayaṭa divya-netrayak-bāṇḍu-vū Śakavarṣayen*. A more serious change has been that of *sasāṭa* (sixty-six) in the date to *susāṭa* (sixty-four).³

In some places where the text on the copper-plates widely diverges from what has been inscribed on stone, the writing is illegible at present, as in lines 5 and 6 of the inscription of Vikramabāhu III. But in most other places, the writing on the stone is quite clear, though the text on the copper-plates has not followed it. This circumstance would lead one to the conclusion that the document as given in the copper-plates is not the result of an attempt made in the time of Rājādhirājasimha, or earlier, to decipher the writing on the stone. The inscription of Bhuvanaikabāhu IV states that that document was inscribed not only on stone, but on copper as well. It is possible that the document originally inscribed on copper was not an exact copy of that inscribed on stone, and that the text as found on the copper-plates, now preserved, was derived from this original copper-plate. But the divergencies noticed when the *Cpt.* is compared with *Gt.*, and the copy in the British Museum, indicate that the original ola copy of the inscription, whether derived from the stone inscription or the copper charter now lost, has been tampered with by scribes who wished to make it conform to their notions about the propriety of things. The *Cpt.* refers to Senālaṅkādhikāra as *raja* (king) and the *Gt.* as *maharaja* (great king) though in different contexts. This is in accordance with traditions still current among the people in the district, and recorded in certain documents dealing with family histories.⁴ But, in the inscription engraved on stone, Senālaṅkādhikāra is nowhere given a royal epithet. Thus it is necessary to have a reliable text of this inscription—one of the principal documents for the study of the Gaṇpaḷa period of Ceylon history—published as it can be deciphered from the stone. The reading now offered is based on an estampage prepared under my direction in 1934, for a photograph of which I am indebted to the Archaeological Commissioner.

The script of this record closely resembles that of the inscription of Dharmakīrti-sthvira at the Gaḍalādeṇi temple, only two miles distant from Laṅkātilaka. A symbol resembling a comma occurs before the beginning and after the end of the Sanskrit and Pali stanzas; this has been represented

3. In spite of the date engraved on the rock being available to him in the portion of this inscription published by H. C. P. Bell, D. M. de Z. Wickremasinghe, in his *Ceylonese Chronology* (*Ep. Zey.*, Vol. III, p. 29), has preferred a scribal error found in a manuscript in the British Museum.

4. See Codrington in JCBRAS., Vol. XXXII (No. 86), pp. 266-7.

in the text and the transliteration by a vertical stroke. The two records also bear the same date, i.e. Śaka 1266, being the third year of Bhuvanaikabāhu.⁵ The language calls for no remarks; such words as require comments will be noticed in footnotes attached to the translation. The document contains a fairly detailed account of the founding of the Laṅkātilaka shrine, mainly due to the efforts of Senālaṅkādhikāra, which is followed by a list of the lands and other donations made to it by the king, Senālaṅkādhikāra and other notables of the period. It ends with imprecations against those who would hinder the continuance of the grant, and exhortations made by the minister to kings and ministers of the present and the future for the maintenance of the shrine. The exhortations are embodied in two Sanskrit stanzas of which an expanded paraphrase is given in Sinhalese. The two Sanskrit stanzas are given in the Tamil inscription also; the second reappears in the inscription at Alavaḷa-amuṇa which also registers donations of lands made to the Laṅkātilaka shrine. The occurrence of variant readings in the second stanza in the different records would justify the conclusion that it was not specially composed on this occasion, but was current among the learned men of the time as a suitable text for utilisation for such purposes, just as is the Pali stanza in which the imprecations are uttered. In addition to the Sinhalese inscription of Bhuvanaikabāhu IV, the text and translation of the Tamil inscription are published here for the first time. Two other inscriptions at Laṅkātilaka, dating from the reigns of Vikramabāhu III and Bhuvanaikabāhu V, and the text and translation of the copper-plates, are also included, so as to have in one place all documents referring to this temple. The rock-inscription at Alavaḷa-amuṇa, too, has been included for the same reason.

I. LAṅKĀTILAKA : SINHALESE ROCK-INSCRIPTION OF BHUVANAİKABĀHU IV

TEXT

- 1 ශ්‍රීගකවම්භියෙන් එක්දහස්දෙසියසැට අවුරුත්තක් පිරුණු සඤ්ඤා මෙකල රජ පැමිණි ත්‍රිසිංහලාධිපතිවර භවනෙනකබාහු නම්වූ මට තුන්වන වෙසග පුරපසළොස්වක
- 2 දෙවාසයෙ මහසංඝයවහන්සේ එක් ව සිභුරුවාණේ පන්හල්ගලමුදුනෙහි කරැවූ නායකපිළිමඅටවිස්සක් හා පිළිමසහසකින් සමුපුණ්ණවූ සතරවෙනිමාලන් නායකපිළි-
- 3 -මසාමීන් හා පිළිමපසකිනුත් සමුපුණ්ණ [කොට] කරවූ තුන්වෙනිමාලන් අටවිසි-
බොධියෙනුත් සුවිසිවිවරණයෙනුත් පිළිම[සය]කිනුත් සමුපුණ්ණ ව මුදුලිවරුන් හැමදෙනත්
- 4 සෙනාවන් එක් ව කරවූ දෙවෙනිමාලන් ශ්‍රීමහාබොධිසාමීන්ට පිට ලා වජ්‍රාසනයෙ වැඩූ හුන් ධාතුදෙසියපන්සැටදෙනකුචහන්සේගෙන් ධාතුරූපයක් පිහිටුවා කළ නායක-
පිළිම-

5. For the interpretation of the date, see Ep. Zey. Vol. IV, pp. 94f.

- 5 සාමීනුත් සිතියම්පිළිම ත්‍රිසහසුයක්දෙනාවහන්සේත් ඉන්ද්‍රබොධිසකයන්වහන්සේත් ලොකෙශ්වරනාථයන්වහන්සේත් සුයාමසන්තුමිනගනුබහවිභණ්ඩුමහෙ-
- 6 -ශ්වරආදිවූ දිව්‍යාරූපත් මෙකීආදදෙනාගෙ දිව්‍යභ්‍රීරූපත් ලංකාවට අරක් ගත් කිහිටෙලිපුල්වන්දෙවිරජ්ජුරුවන්වහන්සේත් සුමනවිභිෂණගණපතිකන්දකු-
- 7 -මාරාදිදෙවිරජ්ජුරුවන්වහන්සේත් බියොවරුන්වහන්සේත් මෙකීබුදුන්දෙවියන්ගෙන් සමුපුණ්ණවූ සෙනාලංකාඅධිකාරනම්වූ මෙකුත් තමන් කරැවූ පාන-
- 8 මාලන් පිළිමගෙයි වැලිකොන්දෙ පටන් කොන්කරැල්ල දක්වා සුපතිරායරුන් ඇතුළුවූ බොහොආචාරිවරුන්ට දුන් වීන් රත්තරිදිපිළිඇතුළුවූදෙසින් මසුරන්-
- 9 අගයෙන් තුන්කෙළසැටලකසයක් [විතැ]රවා අපින් මුදුලිවරුන් සෙනාවන් එක් ව [කරැවූ] මේ ශ්‍රීලංකාතිලකය යි නම් ලා කරවූ මහපිළිමගෙනුත් සෙනාලංකාඅධිකාරයො
- 10 තමන්ගෙ පුත්‍රවනිනාදීන් ලවා කරවූ අටවිසිවියන්මෙපයෙහි පිහිටුවූ සනලොහප්‍රතිමා-
වන් අපිස්මලුවරුන්වහන්සේ ඇතුළුවූ (උ) දෙවාසයෙ මහසංඝයවහන්සේ
- 11 සැපපරිභොගයෙන් සැහපෙනලෙසට කරවූ සංඝාරාමදෙකත් පුෂ්පාරාමඵලාරාමයෙන් යුක්තවූ ශ්‍රීමහාවිහාරය මතු පවත්වන ලෙස ප්‍රතිඝාඨාවක් ඇත මැනවැ යි සෙනාලංකා-
අධිකාරයො
- 12 අපට කීහෙයින් මෙසෙ මැ සි[භු]රුවාණනුවර බද කිරිවවුලෙන් බිජුවටයාළකුත් අපින් මුදුලිවරුනුත් සෙනාවන් එක් වැ අවුතු ව ඇළ අවුණු බඤ්ඤා නර කරවා ලූ අ-
- 13 -ලුත්බදලගොඩින් කුලබුරුබිජු[ස]යාළකුත් පරණබදලගොඩින් බිජුපස්(ස්)යාළකුත් ඇතුළු වැ කුලබුරුබිජුදෙළොස්යාළකුත් මෙහි බද ගසකොළ වල්පිට ඇතු-
- 14 -එවූ තැනුත් සෙනාලංකාඅධිකාරයො තමන්ගේ පමුණුප්‍රවේණියෙන් පිදු සින්දුවල්ල ගොන්වාණිකයෙන් බිජුවටයාළකුත් වසලංකාව[ව]රිඅධිකාරයන්ගෙන් පිදු පර-
- 15-ණබදලගොඩ යකාල්ලෙන් බිජුවටයාළකුත් සන්රුවන්පතිරාජයන්ගෙන් පිදු කසඹි-
ලියාගොඩින් බිජුවටයාළකුත් දිවාණන්ගෙන් නාරම්ගොඩින් බිජුවට-
- 16 යාළකුත් ජයසිංහපතිරාජයන්ගෙන් පිදු දෙල්නොට සිල්පැන්කඤ්ඤර දරාඩ පටන් සපුතලයෙ ඉම දක්ව කුලබුරුබිජුවටදෙළසමුණකුත් සන්තාණෙන් මඩෙල්විටියෙ-
- 17-ල එකකුත් සිභුරුවාණදෙනුවර කුඩාමහන්ඇමදෙනා එක් වැ අවුණු බැඤ්ඤා කණුමුල්ල රුරා තනා දුන්නෙන් පිදු ගොඩවෙලින් බිජුවටයාළකුත් ඇතුළු ව කුලබුරුබිජුව-
- 18-ටදසසන්යාළදෙළොස්මුණක් ඇතුළු වැ මෙය තුවාක් තෙන පරණඉම වූ පරින්දෙන් ගම්මුදුල ගසකොළ වල්පිට ඇතුළුවූ තැනත් සෙනාලංකාඅධිකාරයො
- 19 තමන්ගෙන් පිදු රත්තරිදි ලොකඩ තබෙකඩ ඇතුළුවූ ගරුභාඩන් මෙසෙ මැ තමන්ගේ මඟුල්වහලින් රත්වහලින් ගැනුන්පිරිමීන්ගෙන් වහල්රුදෙසියය-
- 20-කුත් එළසරකින් මීසරකින් සරක්රූරාසරසියයකුත් මෙසෙ මැ විහාරයෙ කළදෙය වව නොකළදෙය කරව දෙවියන්ට බුදුන්ට නිරන්තරයෙන් බත්මල්පහන්පුද ඔලක්කම් පවත්-
- 21-වනලෙසට ලංකාවාසින් තමන්ගේ නම් ලා කළහෙයින් අවුරුද්දකට ගෙයකින් පණමක් නියායෙන් දෙන්ට සැලසුණු පිදෙනිපණමුත් ඇතුළුමඩිසයෙන් පිටමඩිසයෙන් න-

22-වනොටින් අටළොස්දෙනයෙන් ආ වැපාරයන්ගෙන් ගන්න දෙන යම්බඩුයෙකින් සියයට කාලක් නියායෙන් තමෙපන ලියා දුන් සමයශ්‍රියෙන් ලත් සියලුවසකුව ඇතුළු
 23 ඇම ලාභ ම පසක් කොටැ බෙද තුනුරුවන්ට තුන්භාගයකුත් දෙවියන්ට භාගයකුත් මෙකුන්ගෙ දරුමුනුබුරුපරම්පරාවෙන් මෙහි බැඳී පවත්වන කෙනකුන්ට භාගයකු-
 24-ත් සැලැස්වූ නියාවත් මෙයින් කිසිවකට විරුධයක් කොටැ ලොභයෙන් පැහැර ගත් කෙනෙක් ඇත් නම් නරකාදිසතරභයෙහි ඉපැදූ මෙතෙබුදුන් නොදක්නාහු
 25 යැ කාකප්‍ර[තා]දීත් මෙන් බත්පැන් නො ලැබූ වඩාලයන්ටත් අන්ත වැ කවුඩන්-බල්ලන්ට පුත්වූවාහු භම් වෙහි දැනැ || නිණං වා යදි වා කටයං පුප්ඵං වා යදි වා ඵලං යො භරෙ බුබභොග-
 26-සු මභාපෙතො භවිසුති || කියා ශ්‍රීමුඛපාඨ හෙයින් මෙලොපරලොදෙකි ම සැප විඤ්ඤා කැමති උත්තමයන් විසින් මින් කිසිවකට ආශාවක් නො කොට බසකින් අකුර-
 27-ක්වීවරකින් මෙපින්කමට සහය වී කළදෙය වව නොකළදෙය කරව පවත්වා ලූ යම් උත්තමකෙනෙක් ඇත් නම් මේකුලය තමන් කළසේ අනුමොදන් වැ දිවසැපත් නි-
 28-වත්සැපත් සාධා ගන්නා පිණිසැ මෙපින්කම මතු පවත්වන ලෙස භවනෙකබාහු නම්වූ මා විසින් තමෙපතෙයින් මෙශිලාලෙඛයෙහිත් ලියව දෙනලද [[*] එසෙ හෙයින්
 29 සෙනාලංකාඅධිකාරයෙන් මෙසෙවූ ආරාධනාවක් කෙරෙත් || අසා පුණ්‍යසා යසුනා-තා තප්පාදවයජං රජ: [[*] සෙනාලංකාධිකාරීනෙහා කුරුතෙ මුඤ්ඤිති පුණ්‍යවත් [[[*] මෙ පින්කම යම් උත්තමයක්හු විසින් බ-
 30-සකින් අකුර[කින් වත්] සහය ව රක්නාලැබේ ද ඵලත්තමයගෙ ශ්‍රීපාදධූලි සෙනා-ලංකාඅධිකාර නම්වූ මා විසින් සුවඤ්ඤාලේසමුභයක් මෙන් මගේ ඉස්මුඤ්ඤානන් පුදනලදී || සංරක්ඛ-
 31 -නම් ධම්මමනෙකරුපඤ්ඤාලේසමුභයක් මුඤ්ඤිති යාවනෙ'සො [[*] ජාතානතරෙත්තානපි ජායමානාන් මනත්‍රීචරාන්චොත්තානපනානභුත්‍රී: [[[*] සමුපුණ්ණවූ මේකුලෙධම්මය උපන් රාජොත්තමයන්ව-
 32-හන්සේ විසිනුත් උපදින රාජොත්තමයන්වහන්සේ විසිනුත් උපන් අමාත්තොත්තම-යන්වහන්සේ විසිනුත් උපදින අමාත්තොත්තමයන්වහන්සේ විසිනුත් ශ්‍රීසමාච්ඡානි සෙනාව
 33 විසිනුත් මෙධම්මය රක්ෂා කරන පිණිසැ සෙනාලංකාඅධිකාර නම්වූ මා විසින් දසනබසමොධානවූදෙහොන් මුඤ්ඤානේ පිහිටුවා වැඤැ ආරාධනා කරනලදී [[*] ශුභමසතු සම්ප්‍රසංග: [[*]

TRANSCRIPT

- 1 Śrī-Śaka-varṣayen ek-dahas-de-siya-sa-sāṭa avurutdak piruṇu sanda me-kala raja pāmiṇi Trī-Simha[ādhīśvara Bhuvanaikabāhu nam-vū maṭa tun-vana Vesaga pura-pasa]os-vaka
- 2 de-vāsaye maha-saṅghayā-vahanse ek va Siṅguruvāṇe Panhal-gala-mundunehi kārāvū nāyaka-piḷima-aṭa-vissak hā piḷima-sahasakin sampūrṇṇa-vū sataraveni-mālā-t nāyaka-piḷi-

- 3 -ma-sāmin hā piḷima-pasakin = ut sampūrṇṇa [koṭa] karavū tun-veni-māla-t aṭa-visi-Bodhiyen = ut sūvisi-vivaraṇayen = ut piḷima-[saya]kin = ut sampūrṇṇa va mundalivarun hāma-dena-t
- 4 senāva-t ek va karavū deveni-māla-t Śrī-mahā-bodhi-sāmīṇṭa piṭa lā vajrāsanaye vāḍā hun dhātu-de-siya-pan-sāṭa-denaku-vahansegen dhātu-rūpayak pihiṭuvā kaḷa nāyaka-piḷima-
- 5 sāmīn = ut sitiya-piḷima tri-sahasrayak-denā-vahanse-t Maitri-Bodhisatvayan-vahanse-t Lokeśvara-Nāthayan-vahanse-t Suyā-ma-Santuṣita-Śakra-Brahma-Viṣṇu-Mahe-
- 6 -śvara-ādi-vū divvyā-rūpa-t me-kī-āma-denaḅge divvyā-strī-rūpa-t Lamkāvaṭa arak gat Kihireḷi-Upulvan-devi-rajjuruvan-vahanse-t Sumana-Vibhīṣaṇa-Gaṇapati-Kanda-ku-
- 7 -mārādi-devi-rajjuruvan-vahanse-t bisovarun-vahanse-t me-kī-Budun-deviyangen sampūrṇṇa-vū Senā-Lamkā-adhikāra-nam-vū mekun taman kārāvū pāta-
- 8 māla-t piḷima-geyi vālikonde paṭan kot-kārālla dakvā Sthapati-rāyarun ātuḷu-vū boho-ācāri-varuṇṭa dun vin ratran-ridi-piḷi-ātuḷu-vū-deyin masu-ran-
- 9 agayen tun-keḷa-sāṭa-lakṣayak [vitā]ravā api-t mundali-varu-t senāva-t ek va [kārāvū] mē Śrī-Lamkātilakaya yi nam lā kārāvū maha-piḷima-gen = ut Senā-Lamkā-adhikārayo
- 10 taman-ge putra-vanitādin lavā kārāvū aṭa-visi-riyan-maṇḍapayehi pihiṭuvū ghana-loha-pratimāva-t apis-malu-varun-vahanse ātu-ḷu-vū (u)de⁶-vāsaye maha-saṅghaya-vahanse
- 11 sāpa-paribhogayen sātapena-lesāṭa kārāvū saṅghārāma-deka-t puspārāna-phalārāmayen yukta-vū śrī-mahā-vihāraya matu pavat-vana lesa pratiṣṭhāvaka āta mānavā yi Senā-Lamkā-adhikārayo
- 12 apaṭa ki-heyin me-se mā Si[ṅgu]ruvāṇa-nuvara bada Kirivav[u]-ḷen biju-vaṭa-yāḷak = ut api-t mundali-varun = ut senāva-t ek vā amutu va āḷa avuṇu bandavā tara karavā lū A-

6. The letter u is perhaps due to the scribe beginning to write ubhaya-vāsaye for de-vāsaye.

- 13 -lut-Badalagoḍin kumburu-biju-[sa]-yāḷak = ut Paraṇa-Badalagoḍin biju-pass⁷-yāḷak = ut ātuḷu vā kumburu-biju-doḷos-yāḷak = ut mehi bada gasa-koḷa val-piṭa ātu-
- 14 -ḷu-vū tāt = ut Senā-Laṃkā-adhikārayo taman-gē pamuṇu-pra-veniyen pidū Sitdavulla Gonvāṇikayen biju-vaṭa-yāḷak = ut Vasa-Laṃkā-[va]ri⁸-adhikārayangen pidū Para-
- 15 -ṇa-Badalagoḍa Yakāllen biju-vaṭa-yāḷak = ut Satruvan-patirāja-yangen pidū Kasambiliyāgoḍin biju-vaṭa-yāḷak = ut Divāṇangen Nāramgoḍin biju-vaṭa-
- 16 yāḷak = ut Jayasimha-patirājayangen pidū Deltota Silpān-kandure darāṇḍa paṭan Saputalaye ima dakva kumburu-biju-vaṭa-dolos = amuṇak = ut Santāṇen maḍel-viṭiye-
- 17 -la⁹ ekak = ut Siṅguruvāṇa-de-nuvara kuḍā-mahat-āma-denā ek vā avuṇu bāndā kaṇu-mul udurā tanā dunnen pidū Goḍavelin biju-vaṭa-yāḷak = ut ātuḷu va kumburu-biju-va-
- 18 -ṭa-dasa-sat-yāḷa-doḷos = amuṇak ātuḷu vā meya tuvāk tena paraṇa-ima vū paritden gam-mundala gasa-koḷa val-piṭa ātuḷu-vū tāna-t Senā-Laṃkā-adhikārayo
- 19 tamangen pidū ratran ridi lokaḍa tambakaḍa ātuḷu-vū garu-bhāṇḍa-t me-se mā taman-gē magul-vahalin ran-vahalin gānun-pirimin-gen vahal-rū-desiyaya-
- 20 -k = ut eḷa-sarakin mī-sarakin sarak-rū-sāra-siyayak = ut me-se mā vihāraye kaḷa-deya vava no-kaḷa-deya karava deviyāṇṭa Buduṇṭa nirantarayen bat-mal-pahan-puda olakkam pavat-
- 21 -vana-lesāṭa Laṃkā-vāsin taman-gē nam lā kaḷa-heyin avurutda-kaṭa geyakin paṇamak niyāyen denṭa sālasuṇu pideni-paṇam = ut ātuḷu-maḍighayen piṭa-maḍighayen na-

- 22 -va-toṭin aṭaḷos-deṣayen ā vāpārayangen ganna dena yam-baḍuyekin siyayaṭa kālak niyāyen tamba-pata liyā dun samaya-śriyen lat siyalu-vastuva ātuḷu
- 23 āma lābha ma pasak koṭā bedā tunuruvaṇṭa tun-bhāgayak = ut mekun-ge daru-munuburu-paramparāven mehi bāndi pavatvana kenakuṇṭa bhāgayak = u-
- 24 -t sālāsvū niyāva-t meyin kisivakaṭa viruddhayak koṭā lobhayen pāhārā gat kenek āt nam narak = ādi-satara-apāyehi ipādā Mete-Budun no-daknāhu
- 25 yā kāka-pre[tā]dīn men bat-pān nolābā caṇḍālayaṇṭa-t anta vā kavuḍan-ballāṇṭa put-vūvāhu nam veti dānā¹⁰ || Tiṇam vā yadi vā kaṭṭham puppam vā yadi vā phalam yo hare Buddha-bhoga-
- 26 -ssa mahāpeto bhavissati || kiyā Śrī-mukha-pāṭha heyin me-lo-para-lo-dek-hi ma sāpa vindinā kāmati uttamayan visin min kisivakaṭa āśāvak no koṭa basakin akura-
- 27 -k-vicarakin mē-pin-kamaṭa sahaya vī kaḷa-deya vava no-kaḷa-deya karava pavatvā lū yam uttama-kenek āt nam me-kuśalaya taman kaḷa-sē amumodan vā diva-sāpat ni-
- 28 -van-sāpat sādāhā gannā piṇisā mē-pin-kama matu pavatvana lesa Bhuvanaikabāhu nam-vū mā visin tamba-pateyi-t me-śilālekha-yehi-t liyava dena-lada[|*] E-se heyin
- 29 Senā-Laṃkā-adhikārayo-t me-se-vū ārādhānāvak keret || Asya puṇyasya yas = trātā tat = pādadvayajam rajaḥ [|*] Senā-Laṃkā = dhikāriṇdro¹¹ kurute mūrdhni puṣpavat [|*] Mē-pin-kama yam uttamayak-hu visin ba-
- 30 -sakin aku[rakin vat] sahāya-va raknā-lābē da c-uttamayage śrī-pāda-dhūli Senā-Laṃkā-adhikāra nam-vū mā visin suvanda-mal-samūhayak men magē is-mundunen pudana-ladi¹¹ || Saṃ-rakṣi-

7. Read pas.

8. The Tamil inscription gives this name as *Vacādigāriḷaḷ*. Cpt. and Gt. have *Vāsala-karuvū-adhikārayan*.

9. Cpt. has *maṅgul-piṭiyela*.

10. Two curved vertical strokes indicate the beginning as well as the end of this verse.

11. Read °*kārīndraḷ*.

- 31 -tvam¹² dharmmam-anaika¹³ -rūpam = baddhāñjalim¹⁴ = mūrdhani yācate 'sau [[*] jātā[n*] narendrān = api jāyamānān mantriśvarāns = c = ānya-janān bahu-śrīḥ [[*] Sampūrṇa-vū mē-kuśala-dharmmaya upan rājottamayan va-
- 32 -hansē visin = ut upadina rājottamayan-vahansē visin = ut upan amāttottamayan-vahansē visin = ut upadina amāttottamayan-vahansē visin = ut śrī-samṛddhi-āti-senāva
- 33 visin = ut mē-dharmmaya rakṣā karana piṇisā Senā-Laṅkā-adhikāra nam-vū mā visin dasa-nakha-samodhāna-vū-dohot mundunē pihituvā vāndā ārādhana karana-ladī [[*] Śubham = astu sarvva-jagataḥ[[*].

TRANSLATION

[L. 1] When One Thousand Two Hundred and Sixty-six years had been completed in the era of the illustrious Śaka (king)—on the fifteenth of the bright half of Vesagā¹⁵ in the third year of me, named Bhuvanaikabāhu who has attained to the sovereignty at this time.

[Ll. 2-12] Whereas Senā-Laṅkā-adhikāra intimated to us that it would be desirable if there be an endowment¹⁶ for the maintenance in the future of this illustrious great monastery (*vihāra*) which was established on the summit of (the rock called) Panhālgala in Siṅguruvaṇa¹⁷ by the two venerable Communities¹⁸ of the eminent Saṅgha, which includes the great image-house established with the name of Śrī Laṅkātilaka consisting of the fourth storey complete with twenty-eight principal images and a thousand other images, the third storey which was caused to be constructed complete with Its Lordship the Principal Image and five other images, the second storey which is completed with (the representations of) the twenty-eight Trees of Wisdom (*Bodhi*) and the twenty-four Predictions,¹⁹ caused to be constructed conjointly by all the chiefs (*mudali*) and the army,

12. Read *saṃrakṣitum*.

13. Read *aneka*.

14. Read *baddhāñjalir*.

15. *Vesak* (Skt. *Vaiśākha*), April—May.

16. *Pratiṣṭhāvaka* in 1. 11.

17. Now *Siṅguruvaṇa*.

18. The community of *bhikkhus* residing in villages, and the forest-dwelling community.

19. The meeting of Gautama Buddha in previous births with former Buddhas beginning with Dīpaṅkara.

and the lowermost storey which is complete with images of Buddha and gods, to wit, Its Lordship the Principal Image seated on the Diamond Throne (*vajrāsana*) with back to Its Lordship the illustrious great Bodhi-tree, which (Image) has been made by having installed within it a relic-image containing two hundred and sixty-five Lordships of relics, with three thousand Lordships of painted images (including the images of) the Lord Maitrī Bodhisattva, Lord Lokeśvara Nātha²⁰, the forms of the divinities beginning with Suyāma,²¹ Santuṣita,²² Śakra, Brahma, Viṣṇu and Maheśvara, the images of the divine consorts of all these aforesaid personages, the images of the Lord, the divine king Kihireḷi Upulvan,²³ who has taken (upon himself) the protection of Laṅkā, and the divine kings Sumana,²⁴ Vibhīṣaṇa, Gaṇapati, Kandakumāra and others and their consorts—which (storey) was caused to be constructed by this personage himself, namely Senā-Laṅkā-adhikāra, and which (image-house) was caused to be constructed by us, our chiefs (*mudali*) and the host together, having spent thirty-six millions in *masuran* reckoning on account of things including paddy, gold, silver and cloths given to many artisans including Sthapati-rāyara, from the time the base-moulding (*vāli-kōnda*) was started up to the completion of the finial of this image-house—which (*vihāra*) includes the image of solid bronze, installed in the pavilion measuring twenty-eight cubits, which was caused to be constructed by Senā-Laṅkā-adhikāra through his sons and the ladies of his household, the two convents for monks established so that their lordships the members of the great communities of the two fraternities, including the elders of moderate wants,²⁵ may rest there with comfort, and which comprises flower gardens and orchards of fruit trees—as it was so intimated, we have ordered) in this wise.

[Ll. 12-24] (An extent of field sufficient for) the sowing of a *yāla* of seed (paddy) in Kirivavula within the township of Siṅguruvaṇa, (an extent of) fields (sufficient for) the sowing of six *yālas* of seed (paddy) in New Badalagoḍa, which has been established by the construction anew of channels and a dam by us, our chiefs (*mudali*) and the host conjointly, (an extent of field sufficient for) the sowing of five *yālas*²⁶ of seed (paddy) in Old Badalagoḍa and lands appertaining thereto, including trees and forests, (an extent of field sufficient for) the sowing of a *yāla* of seed (paddy) from

20. Avalokiteśvara. See *CJSG.*, Vol. II, pp. 52ff.

21. The presiding deity of the Yāma heaven.

22. The presiding deity of the Tusita heaven.

23. For this deity, see *ASC. Memoirs*, Vol. VI, pp. 19ff.

24. The god of Adam's peak (Samaṇa-kanda).

25. *Apis-maluvarun*. *Apis* = *P. appiccha, malu*, 'old' is equivalent to *P. therā*.

26. A measure of capacity. See *Ep. Zey.*, Vol. III, pp. 183f.

Gonvāṇika in Sitdavulla, granted by Senā-Laṁkā-adhikāra from among the heritable lands belonging to him ; (an extent of field sufficient for) the sowing of a *yāla* of seed (paddy) from Yakālla in Old Badalagoḍa granted from the property of Vasa Laṁkā-vari-adhikāra ;²⁷ (an extent of field sufficient for) the sowing of a *yāla* of seed (paddy) from (the property) of Satruvan-patirāja²⁸ in Kasambiliyāgoḍa ; (an extent of field sufficient for) the sowing of a *yāla* of seed (paddy) from Nāramgoḍa which is a donation from Divāṇa ; (an extent of) field (sufficient for) the sowing of twelve *amunas*²⁶ of seed paddy from the property of Jayasimha-patirāja in Deltota, (which field) extends from the edge of the stream called Silpānkandura up to the boundary of Saputala, one *maḍel-viṭiyela*²⁹ from Santāna ; an extent of field sufficient for the sowing of a *yāla* of seed paddy from Goḍavela dedicated as it was prepared by having dams constructed and the stumps and roots removed, and granted conjointly by everybody high and low in the two townships of Siṅguruvāna ; house-sites,³⁰ trees and forests appertaining to the aforesaid lands altogether amounting to seventeen *yālas* and twelve *amunas* in accordance with their boundaries as of old ; articles for common use of the Saṅgha (*garu-bhāṇḍa*) including (vessels of) gold, silver, bronze and copper, offered by Senā-Laṁkā-adhikāra from his own properties ; two hundred slaves, male and female, from among the slaves that he had acquired at marriage³¹ and slaves purchased;³² and four hundred head of cattle comprising neat cattle and buffaloes likewise offered by Senā-Laṁkā-adhikāra ; the dues called *pideni-panam* settled so that one *panama* be given every year from a house, in consideration of the fact that this shrine was established by the people of Laṁkā in their own name, and for the purpose of improving what has been done and causing what has not been done to be done, of maintaining without cessation the offerings of cooked rice, flowers and lamps to the Buddha and the gods, and for conducting audiences ; a levy of a quarter per cent, at the Inner Customs House and the Outer Customs House,³³ of the value of whatever merchandise purchased or sold

27. See note 8 above. *Vasa* is the personal name, and *Laṁkā-vari-adhikāra* is the designation of an office. This dignitary was probably entrusted with the administration of the revenues (*vari*, T. *vari*) of the kingdom.

28. Dipaṅkara-thera, at whose request the *Paḍasādhana-ṭikā* was composed by Śrī Rāhula, resided at a *pariveṇa* named Sattaratana (Satruvan).

29. The significance of this term is not clear. The corresponding passage in the Tamil version has 'an allotment of forest called Viṭiyela for supplying oil for sacred lamps'.

30. *Gam-mudala*. The corresponding word in the Tamil version (l. 13) is *ūr-nattaṅgaḷ*. See *Ep. Zey.*, Vol. IV, p. 311, n. 2.

31. *Maḡul-vahalin*.

32. *Ran-vahalin*.

33. *Āṇḷu-maḡighaya* and *piṭi-maḡighaya*. The word *maḡigha* occurs in an inscription of Līlavati found at Anurādhapura, and has been incorrectly read as *masisa* (*Ep. Zey.*, Vol. I, p. 180). In that document, it is stated that a *maḡigha* was set up at Anurādhapura in order to levy certain stipulated dues

by merchants coming from the nine seaports or the eighteen countries in accordance with the agreement³⁴ engraved on copper and granted—all this has been settled (on this *viḥāra*) with the stipulation that all revenues, including the goods received as above, shall be divided into five shares, out of which three shares shall appertain to the Three Jewels, (i.e. the Buddha, the Dhamma and the Saṅgha), one share to the gods and one share to any person descended in the succession of sons and grandsons of this Senā-Laṁkā-adhikāra, who is attached to this establishment and maintains it.

[Ll. 24-28] Should there be any persons who contravene anything from these as stated above, and forcibly appropriate anything through avarice, they will be born in the four evil states of existence such as hells, and will not be able to see Mete Budun (the future Buddha Maitreya) ; like crows and dogs they will not obtain food or drink, they will become more despised than the *caṇḍālas* and will become the sons of crows and dogs. Should there be any noble persons who, having known this, and in view of the scriptural text³⁵ which says 'Whosoever takes away anything out of the possession of the Buddha, be it a blade of grass, a stick of wood, a single flower or a fruit, he will become a monstrous goblin', wish to enjoy happiness both in this world and in the other world, who not desiring anything out of this, support this meritorious action even by a mere word or a mere letter, improve what has been done, cause to be done what has not been done and maintain (it)—should there be such high-souled persons—they will share in this meritorious action just as they themselves have done it, and realise the happiness of Heaven and the happiness of Nirvāṇa. And to that end and in order that this act of merit may be maintained in the future, this edict has been granted by me named Bhuvanaikabāhu, having had it recorded on copper-plates and in this stone inscription.

[Ll. 28-33] Therefore, Senā-Laṁkā-adhikāra, too, makes an exhortation of this manner. 'Whoever be the protector of this charitable endowment, Lord Senā-Laṁkādhikārin places the dust on his (i.e. that person's)

from merchants. The word is obviously compounded of *maḍi* (*maḍu* = Skt. *maṇḍapa*) and *ge*, the *g* being erroneously aspirated in pronunciation. In ancient India and Ceylon, the designation of the officer in charge of the collection of customs dues was derived from *maṇḍapa* (*Ep. Zey.*, Vol. III, p. 256). In later Kandyan times *maḍige* was the bullock cart department, a meaning which does not suit the context in which the word occurs in the present document.

34. *Samaya-śriyen*. The word *samaya-śrī* does not occur in any other document. *Samaya* means 'an agreement or an arrangement' and perhaps we have to read *samayāśrayen* in place of *samayaśriyen*. For the corresponding Tamil expression *maḍiṇen-viṣayam*, see note 55, below. If the syllable *śrī* was the royal sign-manual in the Gaṁpaḷa period, as it was during Kōṭṭe and Kandy times, the compound *samaya-śrī* would have meant an agreement on which the royal sign-manual had been affixed.

35. The Pāli stanza which begins *tiṇam vā*, and is found in many late grants referred to as an utterance of the Buddha, is apocryphal.

two feet like a flower on his own head.’³⁶ ‘Should this act of merit be protected, having rendered support to it even with a mere word or a letter by any noble person, the dust on the illustrious feet of that eminent personage is honoured by me, named Senā-Lamkā-adhikāra, by having it placed on my head as if it were a cluster of fragrant flowers’.

‘(This minister) of diverse splendour, in order to protect this charity of many forms, having contracted his fingers on his head, beseeches (to that end) lords of men, powerful ministers and other personages who are already born or will be born in the future.’³⁶

‘So that this complete charity may be protected by noble kings who are already born, noble kings who will be born, noble ministers who are already born and noble ministers who will be born, and that this charity may be protected by the members of the hosts possessing splendour and prosperity, by me, named Senā-Lamkā-adhikāra, they are beseeched having saluted them, placing on my head my two hands with their ten nails brought together’.

May there be happiness for the whole world.

II. LANKĀTILAKA: INSCRIPTION OF VIKRAMABĀHU III

TEXT

1-සිරිසඟබොග්ගිවික්‍රමබාහු නම්වූ මට තුන්වනු උදුවපැ පුරදක³⁷ ස්වර්ණමොක්‍ෂසමපන්නිය සාධා ගන්නා පිණිස ලංකාතිලකරජමහාවිහාරයේ නායකපිළිමසාමීන්ට මාගේ නාමයෙන් ද-

2-වස්සනා බන් පුදන ලෙසට ගොඩරට බද පටියේගම්³⁸ හා මෙහි බද ගම්මුදල ගසකොළ වල්පිට මිනිසා සතා ඇතුළුව සියල්ල විරාත්කාලයක් පවත්නාලෙසට මගෙන් ලොවුතුරා-බුදුන්ට පිදුබවටත්

3 ඇපාණ වහා [[*] මෙවනුවකදවස මාගෙනුත් රබ්බොගමුව හා මෙහි බද ගම්මුදල ගසකොළ වල්පිට මිනිසා සතා ඇතුළුව සියල්ල^[*]ක් [මට] උභයලොකාභිසිඨිය පිණිස දෙවියන් බුදුන් ස-

4 -හිත ලංකාතිලකරජමහාවිහාරය සන්නක කොට මාගෙන් විරාත්කාලයක් පවත්නා-ලෙස පිදුබවටත් මෙ අප කළාවූ පින්කමට දැන් වත් ඉදිරියේ දවස වත් බසකින් විවරත් අවුලක් කළකිකෙ-

36. A Sanskrit stanza, the substance of which is given in more detail in Sinhalese immediately afterwards.

5-නෙක් කවුඩාට බල්ලාට පුත්වූවාහු නම් වෙන් තිරිසන්සතරඅපායෙන් ගොඩ නො-දක්නාහු ය [[*] මෙතෙබුදුන් නොදක්නාහු ය [[*] එලෙස නො වැ බසකින් වි-

6-වර සභාය වැ සිටි කෙනෙකුත් ස්වර්ණමොක්‍ෂසමපන සාධා අමාමහනිවන් දක්නාහු ය සාමීන්ගෙනුත් අපගෙනුත් මෙ සිලාලොඛා-

7-ය ලියවා දෙවූ බවට ඇපාණ වම්හ [[*]

TRANSCRIPT

- 1 Sirisaṅgabo-Sri-Vikramabāhu nam-vū maṭa tun-vanu Unduvapā pura-daka³⁷ svargga-mokṣa-sampattiya sādḥā gannā piṇisa Lamkātilaka-raja-mahā-vihāraye nāyaka-piṭima-sāmiṇṭa māge nāmayen da-
- 2 -vas-patā bat pudana lesaṭa Goḍaraṭa bada Paṭṭiyēgam³⁸ hā mehi bada gam-mudala gasa-koḷa val-piṭa minisā satā ātuḷu-vū siyalla cirāt-kālayak pavatnā-lesaṭa magen Lovuturā-Budunṭa pidū-bavaṭa-t
- 3 Āpāṇa vamha [[*] Me-vanu-vaka-davasa māgen=ut Rabbogamuva hā mehi bada gam-mudala gasa-koḷa val-piṭa minisā satā ātuḷu-vū siyal[[a*]k [maṭa] ubhaya-lokārtha-siddhiya piṇisa deviyan Budun sa-
- 4 -hita Lamkātilaka-raja-mahā-vihāraya santaka koṭa māgen cirāt-kālayak pavatnā-lesa pidū-bavaṭa-t me apa kaḷā-vū pin-kamaṭa dān vat idiriye davasa vat basakin vicara-t avulak kaḷa-ki-ke-
- 5 -nek kavuḍāṭa ballāṭa put-vūvāhu nam vet tirisān-satara-apāyen goḍa no daknāhu ya Mete-Budun no-daknāhu ya [[*] E-lesa no vā basakin vi-
- 6 -cara sahāya vā siti kenekun svargga-mokṣa-sampata sādḥā amā-maha-nivan daknāhu ya svāmingen=ut apagen=ut me-silālekhyā=
- 7 -ya liyavā devū-bavaṭa Āpāṇa vamha [[*].

37. Read *dasa-vaka*.
38. *Paṭṭiyēgama* would be a more preferable form ; but the *virāma* sign of the last *akṣara* is quite clear.

TRANSLATION

On the tenth day of the waxing moon in (the month of) Unduvap³⁹ of the third year of me, Sirisaṅgabo Śrī Vikramabāhu by name, Paṭṭiyegama, situated in Goḍarata, with everything appertaining hereto, including the house-site of the village, forests, serfs and animals, was dedicated from me to the Supermundane Buddha, so that the gift may continue for a long time, and that victuals may be offered daily in my name to Its Lordship the Principal Image in the great royal monastery of Laṁkātilaka in order to obtain for me the happiness of Heaven and Liberation. To this effect, I, the Āpā, testify.

On this selfsame date as aforesaid, the village of Rabbogamu with everything appertaining hereto, including the house-site of the village, trees and shrubs, forests, serfs and animals, was granted, so as to continue for a long time, from me (the Āpā) also, for the attainment of the welfare of both worlds for me, making it a property of the great royal monastery of Laṁkātilaka which contains (images of) deities and the Buddha. Any persons, whether at present or in days to come, who may cause obstruction to this act of religious merit that we have done, even if it be by a mere word, will become equivalent to the sons of crows or dogs, will not see deliverance⁴⁰ from the four states of evil existences, and that of being born an animal, they will not see Mete Budun (the future Buddha Maitreya). Any persons, not being so, who support it even by a mere word, will obtain for themselves the happiness of Heaven and Liberation, and will witness for themselves the state of Nirvāṇa which is Immortality. To the effect that this inscription on stone had been written and granted from His Majesty and from me, I, the Āpā, do testify.

III. LAṆKĀTILAKA : TAMIL INSCRIPTION⁴¹

TRANSCRIPT

- 1 Svasti Śrī [I*] Inda śrī-mahā-vihāram mēl varuttaṇṇaiyir-poruttu idukku pratiṣṭhai-y-iḍuvikka vēnum=enru nammudaiya mandiriga|=ā-

39. Skt. *Mārgasīrṣa*, November—December.

40. *Goḍa*, literally, 'dry land.'

41. This record contains many Grantha letters not only in the Sanskrit *ślokas* but also in the Tamil text. As the press at which this paper is printed is not equipped with Grantha type, it has not been possible to give the text in Tamil characters.

- 2 -ṇa Senā-Laṅgādigāriga| namakku-c-colluvaiyāle nām=ikkōyilukku iḍuvitta rakṣai-y-āvadu [I*] Ciṅguruvānai-nāṭṭil
- 3 Kirivavulai-y-ēngira ūr oru yā|latt=arai-y-um [nām=um mudaliga|]-um nāṭṭavar=um kūḍi-p-pudidāga āvaṇam=um=aḍaittu vāyk-kāl=uṅ=ka-
- 4 -lluvitt=iḍuvitta Pudiya-Vadalagoḍaiyil āru yā|latt=arai-y-um Paḷaiya-Vadalagoḍaiyil aṅju yā|latt=arai-y-um=āga-p-pa-
- 5 -ṇniraṇḍu yā|latt=arai-y-um=āga [ivvū]rga|il nāl=ellaikk=utpaṭṭa kāḍu=m mā-p-puḷi-y-uḷḷiṭṭa tōppu=m ūr-nattam=um
- 6 Senā-Laṅgādigāriga| tammudaiya pārampariyam=āṇa ūrāl=iḍu-vitta Cittāvullai Koṇvāṅikkai-y-ēngira iran-
- 7 -ḍ=ūrāl oru yā|latt=arai-y-um Vacādigāriga|=iḍuvitt=ūr Paḷaya-Vadalagoḍaiyil Yagāllai-y-ēngira vayalāl yā|latt=arai-y-um
- 8 Satruvaṇ-padirāyar=iḍuvitta Kasambiliyagoḍai-y-ēngira ūr oru yā|latt=arai-y-um Divāṇā-uḍaiyār=iḍuvitta Nāraṅ-
- 9 goḍai oru yā|latt=arai-y-um Jayciṅga-p-padirāyar=iḍuvitta Del-gottaiyil paṇṇiraṇḍ = amaṇatt=arai-y-um Sandāṇā-aḍa-
- 10 -viyile tiru-viḷakk=enṇaikk=āga iḍuvitta(Viḍiyela)m=āga kāḍu=m Ciṅguruvānai-nāṭṭavar kūḍi āvaṇam=um (m)aḍaittu vā-
- 11 -ykkāl=uṅ=kalli-y-iḍuvitta Koḍavelai [oru] yā|latt=arai-y-um=āga -y-ippaḍi i-k-kōyilukku nām=um mudaliga|=um nāṭṭa-
- 12 -var=um=āga-k-kūḍi-y-iḍuvitta kṣetram padinelu yā|lattu-p-paṇ-ṇiraṇḍ=amaṇatt=arai-y-um=ivai-y-irriḷa nāl=ellaikk=utpaṭṭa kā-
- 13 -ḍu tenṇa maram [cappu] mā-p-puḷi-y-uḷḷiṭṭa tōppukka|=um ūr-nattaṅga|=um=iḍuvittu Senā-Laṅgādigāriga| tām=i-k-kō-
- 14 -yilukk=iḍuvitta poṇ velli veṅgalam=irumbu mudal=āṇa pūjā-bhāṇḍaṅga|=um ivar tammudaiya kalliyāṇa-aḍi-
- 15 -maiyāy=um kāc=itṭu-k-koṇḍu iḍuvitta āṇ=aḍimai peṇṇ=aḍimai-yāl=iru-nūṛ⁴²=aḍimai-y-um pacu erumai-y-uḷ-
- 16 -ḷiṭṭa māḍu-kaṅru-kāliyāl nāṇūru-rūvam ippaḍi iṭṭa inda Śrī-vihāratṭil=elund=aruḷi-y-irukkira Sarvajṅarga|
- 17 devasthā [naṅ]ga| ivargaḷukku tiruppaṇi ceyvikka[maiyir] po-rutt=um amudu paḍi tiru-viḷakku-t-tiruppaḷiṭṭāma-
- 18 -m kūtt=ōlakkam mudal=āṇa pūcai ivai irrukkum tiru-p-pari-vatṭam ābaraṇam ivai irrukkum [Laṁ]kātilagam e-
- 19 -ṇru irājyavāsiga| pēr = āgaiyil irācciya-vāsiga| ellārum kūḍi āṇḍoṇrukku viṭṭāl=oru paṇam=ā

42. Read *nūr* =

- 20 -ṇḍudōrum kuḍukka-k-kaḍavārgaḷ=āga nām=um mudaligaḷ=um
kūḍi colli maṇ-kalan=taḍuttu poṇ-kalam eḍutt=um taḍutt=um
- 21 vaḷaitt=um taṇḍi-k-koḷḷa-k-kaḍavad=āga āccinai-p-paṇṇinōm [*]
Pura-maḍigaiyāl=um uḷ-maḍigaiyāl=um oṇṇpadu-
- 22 tuṇaiyāl=um paḍiṇeṭṭu tecattil niṇṇum vanda vāṇiyaṅgaḷāl=um
koḷṇ[*]ḍu vanda pala-maṇḍala-carākkukku nūṇṇruk-
- 23 -ku-k-kāl kuḍukkum paḍi maḍiṇeṇ-visayam=āga-k-kūḍi vaittu
k-kuḍuttu cembil=um kallil=um eḷudi-k-kuḍuttārgaḷ ippaḍi
- 24 iḍuvitta rakṣaiyāl vanda vastu-v-ellām=añju kūrāga-p-pagarndu
Buddha-Dharmma-Samgham = āgiya ratnatrayattukku mūṇṇru
kūr=um
- 25 teyvaṅgaḷuk=oru kūr=um Senā-Laṅgādigār[i]gaḷ=uḍaiya vaṅsattile
tōṇṇri inda dharmmatai rakṣittu tiru-p-pa-
- 26 -ṇi ceyvittu-p-pōdugira bandhukkaḷukku oru kūrūm=āga-k-
kaḍaikka paḍi ippaḍi inda dharmmam candrādittavarai naḍakkum
- 27 paḍi cembil=um kallil=um eḷudivitt=iḍuvittom=ippaḍiyai ellārum
priya-p-paṭṭu-k-koḷḷavum [*] Idu-k-koḍu-po-
- 28 -llāngu-manattāl=um niṇaiyād=oliyavum aṇṇriyē idukku virodaṅ
=colli idil cantakam=āṇa vastuvai ācaiyā-
- 29 -le-y-ādal valārkarattāle-y-ādal paṇṇittu-k-koṇḍa pāba-karmma-
-rkkaḷ nūṇṇru muppatt=āru naragaṅgaḷil=um vēndu karai-tara-
- 30 -ṇa-māṭṭār=āy pey vilaṅgu-cādi asurargaḷ = āy = um piṇandu
neḍuṅ=kālam tukkam anubavippārgaḷ = āga pañca-caṇḍāla-ku-
- 31 -lattukk=um antyar=āvārgaḷ = āga nāy kākkai=y-uḷḷiṭṭa vilaṅgu-
cādik=um kaḍai-y-āvārgaḷ⁴³=āga eṇṇumpu kaḍai yāṇai ta-
- 32 -lai eṇṇattu-nāngu-nūr=āyira-kōḍi vilaṅgu-cādiyir=piṇandu karai
kāṇa-māṭṭārgaḷ=āga Maitreya-sarvajñarai-k-kā-
- 33 -ṇa-māṭṭārgaḷ=āgav=um [*] Ippaḍi-y-aṇṇriyile inda tanmattukku
vacana-māṭṭirattāle-y-āgilum cagāyap=paṭṭu idaṇai rakṣi -
- 34 -tta puṇya-kanmarkkaḷ=āṇa-vargaḷ āru teyva-logattil sampatt=um
manuṣya-logattil cakravartti-mahārāja--sampa-
- 35 -ttu maṇḍalika-sampattu brahma-sampattu māra-sampattukkaḷ
=um peṇṇu muḍivile amṛta-mahā-nirvāṇam-eṇṇu collappa-
- 36 -ṭṭa mokṣa-sampattai-y-um peṇṇuvargaḷ [*] Inda dharmma-
karttā-v-āṇa Senā-Laṅgādhigārigaḷ idaṇai rakṣikkaiyir=poruṭṭu
ippa-

43. Read *kaḍaiyavar-āvārgaḷ*

- 37 -ḍiye ārādhnam paṇṇinār [*] Asya puṇyasya yas=trātā tat=
pāda-dvayajam rajah [*] Senā-Laṅgādhikāṇḍra⁴⁴ kurute mūr-
dhni pu-
- 38 -ṣpa-vat [*] Asya puṇyasya inda dharmmataṇai yaḥ yād=oru
sat-puruṣaṇ trātā vacana-māṭṭirattāle-y-āgilum sahāyam paṇṇi
rakṣi-
- 39 -kkirāṇ anda puruṣottamaṇ=uḍaiya pādadvayajam rajah iraṇḍu
kāḷir poḍi-y-inai Senā-Laṅgādhikāṇḍra⁴⁴ Senālaṅgāḍhi-
- 40 gārigaḷ=eṅgira mantri-śreṣṭhaṇ mūrddhi talaiyile puṣpa-vat sugan-
-dham=āṇa pū-p-pōl kurute kūḍāniṇṇār [*] Saṁrakṣitum dharm-
mam=anaika⁴⁵
- 41 -rūpam baddhāñjalim⁴⁶ mūrddha[ni*] yācate'sau [*] jātā[n*]
narendrān=api jāyamānān=mantriśvarān sainya-janān bahu-śriḷ
[*] Asau inda
- 42 mantri-śreṣṭhaṇ anekarūpam pratimā-citraṅgaḷāle aneka-prakā-
-ram=āṇa inda dharmmam Laṅgādilagam=eṇṇu pērai-y-uḍaiya
dharmmati-
- 43 -ṇai saṁrakṣitum rakṣikkai [ā]ga mūrddhi talaiyilē baddhāñ-
-jalim daśa-nakha⁴⁶ prabhayālē vilaṅgi kuvindappattā añjaliyai-
y-uḍai-
- 44 -yar=āya jātā[n*] narendrān=api ippoludu vattikkira *rājarkkaḷai*
y-um jāyamānān mēṇ=tōṇṇrugira *rājarkkaḷai-y-um* mantriśvarān
ip-
- 45 -pōlud=uḍāṇa mantrigaḷai-y-um mēḷ=uḍāgira mantrigaḷai-y-um
sainyanān ippoludu vattikkira nāṭṭavarai-y-um mēḷ varugira na-
- 46 -ṭṭavarai-y-um bahuśriḷ anekam=aiśvariyattai-y-uḍaiyar=āy=iruk-
kiṇa inda mantri yācate vēṇḍi-k-koṇḍār [*]
Śubham=astu [*]

TRANSLATION

[Ll. 1-13] 'Hail ! Prosperity ! Whereas our minister, Senā-Laṅgādi-
gārigaḷ, intimated to us that an endowment should be assigned to this, so
that this illustrious great *vihāra* should continue to exist in the future, (the
lands for its) maintenance caused to be granted to this shrine by us are as
follows :—

44. Read *Senā-Laṅgādhikāṇḍraḥ*.45. Read *aneka-*46. Should be *baddhvā 'ñjalim* or *baddhāñjalir*. The Tamil paraphrase which follows indicates
that *baddhāñjalir* was the reading intended by the author of the verse.

An allotment⁴⁷ of field one *yāla* (in sowing extent) in the village named Kirivavulai⁴⁸ in the district of Ciṅguruvāṇai; an allotment of field, six *yālas* (in sowing extent) in New Vadalagoḍai, which has been established by constructing a dam anew and the digging of channels by us, our chiefs (*mudaliga!*) and the people (acting) together; an allotment of field five *yālas* (in sowing extent) at Old Vadalagoḍai; amounting to allotments of field of twelve *yālas* (in sowing extent) and comprising the forests, gardens, including mango and tamarind trees, and sites for houses within the four boundaries of these villages; an allotment of field one *yāla* (in sowing extent) in the two villages called Cittāvullai and Koṇvāṇikkai, caused to be granted, from among the estates which belong to him as inherited villages, by Senā-Laṁgādigāriḡa!; an allotment of field one *yāla* (in sowing extent) in the field called Yaḡallai in Old Vadalagoḍai, caused to be granted by Vacādigāriḡa!; an allotment of field, one *yāla* (in sowing extent), in the village called Kasambiliyagoḍai, caused to be granted by Satruvan-padirāyar; an allotment of field, one *yāla* (in sowing extent), in Nāraṅgoḍai, caused to be granted by Lord Divāṇā; an allotment of field, twelve *amaṇas* (in sowing extent), in Delgoṭṭai, caused to be granted by Jayaciṅga-padirāyar; a forest called Viḍiyela⁴⁹, for supplying oil for sacred lamps, caused to be granted from the Sandānā forest; an allotment of field one *yāla* (in sowing extent) in Koḍavelai, which has been established by the construction of a dam and the digging of channels by the people of the Ciṅguruvāṇai district acting together,—thus the fields caused to be granted to this shrine by us, our chiefs (*mudaliga!*) and the people together total in extent to seventeen *yālas* and twelve *amaṇas*; these lands, free of taxes, comprising the forests, the gardens including coconut, *cappu*,⁵⁰ mango and tamarind (trees), and sites for houses in the villages within their four boundaries, were caused to be granted.

[Ll. 13-27] By Senā-Laṁgādigāriḡa! himself, have been caused to be granted to this shrine, utensils for religious worship made of gold, silver, bronze, iron and other metals, and two hundred slaves from among the male slaves and female slaves comprising the slaves that he had (received as dowry) at marriage, and those that he had purchased by paying money; and four hundred head of cattle including neat cattle and buffaloes from herds of bulls and calves. And for the purpose of conducting the sacred services, for offerings of food, for lamps, for garlands, for dances, for audi-

47. *Arai*, 'assigned portion of an area'; see *Tamil Lexicon*, s.v.

48. For this and other place names in the Tamil document, compare the corresponding names in the Sinhalese record.

49. The Sinhalese has *maḍel-viṭiyala*.

50. Sinhalese *sapu*.

ences and other observances—for the continuance of these—for robes and ornaments—for the maintenance of these, to the Omniscient Lord (Buddha) who has been graciously pleased to manifest Himself and remain in this illustrious *vihāra*, and to the abodes of divinities—to these in the shrine thus established, the inhabitants of the realm have all joined together and pledged themselves to pay one *paṇam* a year from each house every year, since the shrine has been given the name Laṅkātilagam—the name of all the inhabitants of the realm.

Accordingly, we and the chiefs (*mudaliga!*) assembled together and having spoken (to that effect) made order that it is obligatory to exact this impost⁵¹ even by having seized the earthen vessels (of the household),⁵² by taking away gold and jewellery,⁵³ by seizing them or by (placing people) in restraint.⁵⁴ We also, having assembled and fixed as a matter concerning the computation of dues⁵⁵ that, from the outer customs-house and from the inner customs-house,⁵⁶ there shall be levied a quarter per cent of the value of merchandise from various countries brought by merchants coming through the nine seaports from the eighteen countries, and having caused (this decision) to be engraved on copper, granted (such dues to the shrine).

51. For the meaning 'impost' given here to *taṇḍi*, compare the phrase *palar = um kai-vanda-paḍi taṇḍi-k-kolgaiyāle* occurring in a Coḷa inscription (*SIL.*, Vol. VI, No. 58; see also Nilakanta Sastri, *The Coḷas*, Vol. II, Madras, 1937, p. 343). Compare also the term *ge-daḍ*, occurring in tenth-century Sinhalese inscriptions (*Ep. Zey.* Vol. I, p. 250), which was probably a levy on each household similar to that referred to in the present record.

52. *Taḍuttu*, lit., 'having hindered, stopped or obstructed.' Perhaps we have here an allusion to a measure adopted by royal officers to make unwilling people pay dues to the government, i.e. by taking hold of the earthen vessels in a household and keeping them, depriving the persons concerned of the means of cooking their meals.

53. *Poṇ-kalam* may also be translated as 'vessels of gold.'

54. *Vaḷaitt = um*. One of the many meanings of the verb *vaḷai* is 'to hinder, obstruct.' Perhaps in this word there is a reference to the practice known as *vālūkme dāmīma*, which was resorted to in ancient Ceylon for exacting dues. See F. A. Hayley, *Sinhalese Laws and Customs*, p. 516 and *Ep. Zey.*, Vol. III, p. 91f. The whole phrase *maṇ-kalan-taḍuttu poṇ-kalam eḍutt = um taḍutt = um vaḷaitt = um* is rather obscure in significance, and has not been met with in any other document. The interpretation given here therefore has to be treated as tentative.

55. *Madiṇeṇ-viṣayam* :—This too is an expression which, to my knowledge, has not been found elsewhere. A word of Tamil origin, still in use in colloquial Sinhalese, indicates that there was a dialectical Tamil word *madiṇeṇ* known to the Sinhalese in the past. An indoor game prevalent among the Sinhalese villagers is called *madiṇci* or *madiṇēci*. In this game, one person has to pronounce, after a show of computation, whether a pile of nuts covered by the hand of another consists of an odd or even number. In *madiṇci* as well as in *madiṇēci*, the final syllable *ci* or *ēci* is the Tamil suffix *-ci* or *-cci*. *Madi* and *madiṇeṇ* thus have the same significance, and the latter form is obviously not preserved in the Sinhalese words derived from them. *Madiṇeṇ* may be analysed into two components, *madiṇ* and *eṇ*; *madiṇ* itself formed by the addition of the locative suffix *iṇ* to *madi* (= Skt. *mati*). *Eṇ* means computation. *Madi* in Malayālam has the meaning of 'taxes, especially port dues.' (See H. Gundert, *Malayalam and English Dictionary*, s.v.). The expression *madiṇeṇ-viṣayam* occurs in our document in a passage dealing with port dues, and it is certain therefore that the word is used here in that sense. The corresponding term in the Sinhalese inscription is *samayaṣṭriya*; see note 34 above.

56. *Puṇa-maḍigai* and *uḷ-maḍigai* correspond to *ātuḷu-maḍigha* and *piṭa-maḍigha* in the Sinhalese record. See note 33 above.

All incomes derived from the endowments thus granted shall be divided into five shares, out of which three shares will go to the Three Jewels, namely the Buddha, Dharma and Saṃgha, one share to the gods, and one share to a kinsman or descendant of Senā-Laṅgādigāriḡa, who, having appeared in his lineage, protects this charity and is engaged in the performance of the sacred services—so it has been ordained.

In order that this charity may last as long as the moon and the sun, this order was written on copper as well as stone, and granted. In this manner shall every one accept (this order) with gratification.

[Ll. 27-37] Apart from any loss caused unintentionally, those sinners who, out of deceitful or evil intention, having spoken against this charity, either out of greed for the properties belonging to this shrine, or due to violence, confiscate and take it for themselves, will be burnt in the one hundred and thirty-six hells, and will be unable to see the limit thereof; they will be born as fiends, various classes of beasts and *asuras*, and suffer torment for a long time; they will become inferior even to the five *caṅḡāla* castes, and will become more degraded even than creatures including crows and dogs; they will be born among the eighty-four million classes of animals, at the end of whom is the ant and at the head is the elephant, and will not see the limit of such existence; they will not be able to see Maitreya, the Omniscient One.

On the other hand, those persons of virtuous actions, who, even by a mere word, support this charity and protect it, will obtain the affluence of the six celestial worlds, the affluence of a great universal monarch, the affluence of a territorial magnate in the world of men, the affluence of Brahmas or the affluence of Māras, and in the end shall realise the abundance of Liberation which is called the great cessation into Immortality. And the founder of this charity, Senā-Laṅgādhigāriḡa, for the sake of protecting this, makes an exhortation in this manner.⁵⁷

* * * * *

[Ll. 37-46.] Whoever may be that virtuous person who, even by a mere word, supports and sustains this charity, the dust on the two feet of that noble personage, the excellent minister called Senā-Laṅgādhigāriḡa, places on his head as if it were a fragrant flower.

* * * * *

57. The Tamil text here gives the two Sanskrit stanzas which occur in the Sinhalese text also. As the translation of these has been given in the rendering of the Sinhalese text into English, it is not repeated here. Each stanza is followed in the Tamil inscription by a word-to-word gloss in Tamil, which enlarges on the content of the Sanskrit stanzas. The translation that follows is of the Tamil explanation, excluding the Sanskrit words glossed upon.

This pre-eminent minister endowed with fortune of diverse sorts, for the sake of the protection of this charitable foundation bearing the name of Laṅgādilaga, which is (adorned in) diverse manner by images and paintings, with hands placed together on his head, having the fingers thereof illuminated by the lustre of the ten nails, beseeches therefor kings who are flourishing at present as well as kings who would appear in the future, ministers who exist at present and ministers who will come in the future, and also citizens who flourish at present and citizens who will come in the future.

IV. LANKĀTILAKA: INSCRIPTION OF THE REIGN OF BHUVANAİKABĀHU V.

On the rock outside the gate (*vāhalkaḡa*) to the west of the main shrine of Laṅkātilaka there are four lines of writing covering an area of about 5 ft. 7 in. by 1 ft. 4 in. The writing in lines three and four is badly weathered, and not a single word can be deciphered in them. The fourth line appears to end abruptly, suggesting that the engraving of this record had not been completed. The first and second lines refer to the eighteenth year of Bhuvanaika-bāhu who must be the fifth of that name, for the reign of Bhuvanaika-bāhu IV did not run to the eighteenth year. The second line also refers to the *vihāra* and the *devālas*, but the fragmentary nature of the document does not permit us to say definitely in what connection.

TEXT

- 1 ශ්‍රී භුවනෙකබාහුන්ට [අට]-
- 2 -ළොස්වනු මේ විහාරදෙවල
- 3
- 4

TRANSCRIPT

- 1 Śrī-Bhuvanaika-bāhunṡa [aṡa]-
- 2 -ḡos-vanu mē vihāra-devāla
- 3
- 4

TRANSLATION

In the eighteenth year of Śrī-Bhuvanaika-bāhu, this *vihāra* and the *devālas*.....

V. LANĀTILAKA: COPPER—PLATES

The texts of the stone inscriptions of Bhuvanaikabāhu IV and Vikrama-bāhu III given in these plates do not conform to the orthography of the fourteenth century, particularly in the use of n, ṇ, l and ḷ, the orthography then in use in Kandy times being followed. Apart from these orthographical aberrations and insignificant variations noticed in certain words, the copper-plates give that portion of the text of the inscription of Bhuvanaikabāhu IV, concerned with the details of the grant and the imprecatory passages, in conformity with what has been recorded on the rock. It has, therefore, been considered unnecessary to give a translation of this part, i.e. ll. C 4—E 4 of the copper-plates, corresponding to ll. 12—29 of the stone inscription. Some points to be noted in this portion are : the copper-plates refer to an Āpāna, whereas the stone inscription mentions Divāṇan, the text of the copper-plates omits 'Jayasimha' in the name 'Jayasimha-patirāja' and 'Vasa-Lamkā-vari-adhikāra' is called 'Vāsala-karavū-adhikāra'. It also omits the entire passage from me-pinkama up to dena-lada ese heyin found in l. 28 of the stone inscription. This omission minimises the part of the king in the grant to the temple, and correspondingly magnifies that of Senā-Lamkādhikāra. The insertion in the Cpt. of the phrase Mehenavara-vaṁsābhijāta Senā-Lamkādhikārin-vaṣin immediately after the date has the same purpose, achieved by a certain loss of coherency in the document. The Sinhalese text is so irrational in the construction of the long and unwieldy sentence which comprises the greater part of it, that the English translation can hardly reproduce it faithfully.

In the account of the building of the temple, the Cpt. adds much matter not found in the stone inscription. Towards the end, the two exhortatory verses are provided with a Sinhalese paraphrase much more detailed than in the stone inscription, and a third Sanskrit verse, one of common occurrence in land grants both in India and in Ceylon, is added with an expanded version in Sinhalese.

The text of the inscription of Vikramabāhu III given in the Cpt. differs from the inscription on stone only in verbal variations. The tithi in the date which is given as daka for dasa-vaka on the stone, is pasalos-vaka on the copper-plate. The grants of Kīrtti-Śrī-Rajasimha and Rājādhirājasimha given on the last plate are not in the style of Kandyan land-grants in general, but imitate the phraseology of the record of Vikramabāhu III.

I wish to express here my indebtedness to the Venerable Amunugama Rajaguru Siri-Vipassi, Anunayaka Thera of the Malwatte Chapter and

Incumbent of the LanĀtilaka-vihāra, for readily extending to me all necessary facilities for the study of these copper plates as well as the stone inscriptions, and for the many kindnesses shown to me on my visits to his temple in this connection.

TEXT †
A

- 1 ශ්‍රී ශක්වතියෙන් එකවාදනසේසියසඟටඉචුරුද්දක් පිරුනුසඳ මෙකල රජ පැමිනි ශ්‍රීසිංහලාධිපතර භවනේකකතාහුනමවු මට තුන්-
- 2 වනෙනහි මෙනෙතවරවංශාභිජාත සෙනාලංකාධිකාරිනවිසින් වෙසභ පුරපසලොසවක දෙවාසයෙ මහසංඝයාවහන්සේ එකව සිදුරුවානා-
- 3 උඩුනුවර පනහල්ගලමුදුනෙහි දිගින් පුළුලින් ගටගනැරියනක් පුච්ඡුමාණ කළුගලින් බැඳ සමතල කොට ගෙලමයදධිසානමයාකයෙ-
- 4 -හි නොයෙක්ලක්ෂගනන්ගඩඑවෙන් සතරමහල් කොට පුච්ඡුසාහිමුබබසුචෙන් යුක්ත කොට සතරදිසාවෙහි වන්දිකාසල්ලයෙන් පිටත තැන්පස උළුවෙන්
- 5 දෙවැලපසකුන් සමඟ බැඳ නහනලද සිඛවිද්‍යාධරණ්‍යවිමුභසිංහවාසාසුකිබ්බිමකර-පතාදිවිචිත්‍රකමානනයෙන් සමලංගුත කොට වැලිකොඤ්ඤි පට-
- 6 -න් කොත්කැරැල්ල දක්වා දෙතිස්රියනක් බැඳ නහනලද සතරකොනෙහි දගොප්-සතර හා මුදුන්දගොබෙහි රන්කොත් පලඳවා මුදුන්දගොබෙහි දෙරලි දෙ-
- 7-රබා ලවා පොත්ඉළ කොට පිටකනුය ලියවා තබා සමුඤ්ඤවනලදවිත්‍රකමානන-යෙන් කරවූ නායකපිලිමඉටවිසාක් හා පිලිමසහග්‍රයකින් සමුඤ්ඤ
- 8 සතරවෙතිමාලන් වඩුපස්රියන් ඔන්පිලිමසාමිනුන් පිලිමසකිනුන් සමුඤ්ඤ ව කරවූ තුන්වෙතිමාලන් අටවිසිබොධියෙනුන් සුවිසිවිවරණයෙ-
- 9-නුන් පිලිමසහග්‍රයකිනුන් සමුඤ්ඤ ව මුඳලිවරුන් ඇමදෙනාන් සෙනාවන් එකව කරවූ දෙවෙතිමාලන් තාමුමයවූ බොධිවක්‍රයක් සමුඤ්ඤපත්‍රශාඛා-

B

- 1- වෙන් විචිත්‍ර කොට කරවූ ශ්‍රීමහාබොධිසාමීන්ට පිට ලා වජ්‍රසනයෙ වැඩ හුන් ධාතු-දෙසියපන්ඟටදෙනකුචහන්සෙගෙන් ධාතුරූපයක් පිහිටුවා කල නාය-
- 2-කපිලිමසාමිනුන් උභයපාඤ්චයෙහි වාමර ගෙන සිටිනා වඩුපස්රියන් උස දිවාරූප-දෙකකුන් එසේ ම උස ඇති මෙමුත්තාට ලෝකේසරනාට රූපදෙකකුන්
- 3 දිවාසුත්රූපදෙකකුන් කරවා සිතියම්පිලිමසහග්‍රයක්දෙනාවහන්සේන් මිලිතොරණයෙහි ඉක්‍රමුඛවිඤ්ඤාමහෙසරසුයාමසනතුසිතාදිවූ දිවාරූපන් මෙකීඇමදෙ-
- 4-නාගේ දිවාසුත්රූපන් කරවා වියන්සිතනමහිකතිසිතනමිදෙක්හි පන්සියපනස්ජාතකාදින් කරවා දෙරවුපාලයින් කරවා තබා දෙවැලයෙහි ලංකාවට අරගන් කිහිඳ-
- 5 -ලිලපුල්වන්සුමණවිභිෂණගණපතිබන්ධකුමාරාදි දෙවිරජුරුවන්වහන්සේන් බිසො-වරුන්වහන්සේන් කරවා මෙකී බුදුන්දෙවියන්ගෙන් සමුඤ්ඤවූ සෙනාලංකාධිකාරි

† What has been printed as ඊධට (l. E 3), ටජ (l. E 5), ටච (l. E 7) and ඊධා (G 6) are Conjoint letters on the plates.

6 නමිටු මෙකුන් නමේ කරවූ සාකමාලන් ස්වපතිරායරාන් ඇතුළුව බොහොඹාවාරි-
වරන්ට දුන් ඒක රත්නපිටියිදු ඇතුළුවූ දෙසින් මුදුරන් අගයෙන් තුන්කෙලඹටලකසයක් දී
අපිත් මු-
7 -අවිවරුන් සේනාවක් එක කටවු මේඡිලොකාතිලකනමුවපිටිමගෙයි ඉදිරිපිට සේනා-
ලංකාධිකාරයො තමන්ගේ පුත්වනිතාදීන් ලවා කරවූ අවවිසිරියන්මහමඩවසයෙහි ඇ-
8-ලයෙන් මකරනෝරණබොගන ව පිහිටුවූ නමෝ උසමහනට දහස්ගණන්සානලොහ-
යෙන් පුතිවාරාජයක් කරවා මෙකිඤ්ජාදෙවියන්ට මුළුතැන් පිසීමට දිගින් එකොලොස්වි-
9-න් මුළුතැන්ගෙයක් කරවා එමඛපඉදිරියෙහි පුළුදිහිඟගෙයෙහි එකකියවිසිරියන් දිගින්
පුළුදින්න සනරපස්දොකුන් ඔවුනොවුන් ඇඟ නොවදී යන පරිදොත් කළුගල්පසියකු-

C

- 1-න් බැඳ යුතුසනරකොනෙහි වටකළුගලින් සාරසියසකිරියන් සීමාපහුරකුන් බදවා පසවීමදිසාභාගයෙන් දිගින් පලවින් අවරියන් පමන දොමාල්මහවා-
- 2-සලකුන් කරවා එයින් පිටත විහාරරක්ෂාවෙහි නියුක්තදුසිදස්කම්කරුවන් ඉත්තා-
ලෙසට විවිධිකාභසන් ලවා කරවා තබා අසිසමාළුවරුන්ටහන්සෙ ඇතුළු
- 3 වූ දොවාසයෙ මහසංඝයාවහන්සේ භෙරිභොගයෙන් භනපෙනලෙසට කරවූ සංඝාරම-
දොකන් පුෂ්පාරාමේලාරාමයෙන් යුක්තවූ ශ්‍රීමහාවිහාරය මතු පවසන්න-
- 4 ලෙසට පුතිසයාවක් ඇත මැනවැ යි සේනාලංකාධිකාරයො අපට කීගෙයින් මෙසේ
ම සිදුරුවානානුවරබදකිරිවවුලෙන් බිඳුවටයාලකුන් අපිත් මුදලිවරුන්
- 5 සේනාවක් එකව අමුතු ඇලඅවුඳු බදවා කර කරවා ඒ අළුත්බදලගොසින් කුඹුරුබිඳු-
සයාලකුන් පරණබදලගොසින් බිඳුපස්සයාලකුන් ඇතුළු ව කුඹුරුදො-
- 6-ලොස්සාලකුන් මෙහි බද ගසකොල වල්පිට ඇතුළුව තැනුන් සේනාලංකාධිකාරයො
නමන්ගේ පමුනුපුළුච්චියෙන් පිදු හිඳුවුලලගොන්මැනිකයෙන් බිඳුවට-
- 7 යාලකුන් වාසලකරවූඅධිකාරයන්ගෙන් පිදු පරණබදලගොඩ යකාලෙලන් බිඳුවට-
යාලකුන් සන්රුවන්පතිරාජයන්ගෙන් පිදු කසබිලියගොසින් බිඳුවටයාලකුන්
- 8 ඇපානන්ගෙන් පිදු නරණගොසින් බිඳුවටයාලකුන් පතිරාජයන්ගෙන් පිදු දොල්නොට
සිල්පුන්කදුරෙ දරාඩ පටන් සපුනලෙස ඉමි දක්වා කුඹුරුබිඳුවටදොලො-
- 9-සමුනකුන් සනානොන් මතුල්පිටියෙලඵකකුන් සිදුරුවානානුවර කුඩාමහන්ඇම-
දොන් එකව අමුතු ඇලඅවුඳු බැඳ කනුමුල් උදුවා නතා දුන්නන් පිදු ගො-

D

- 1 -ඩවෙලින් බිඳුවටයාලකුන් ඇතුළු ව කුඹුරුබිඳුවටදසසන්යාලදොලෙසමුනක් ඇතුළු ව
මෙයි තුඩක් තැන පරණඉමුවපරිදොත් මෙහි බද ගසකොල
- 2 වල්පිට ඇතුළුව තැනුන් සේනාලංකාධිකාරයො තමන් පිදු රත්න පිදි ලොකඩ තමබකඩ
ඇතුළුව ගරුභාවන් මෙසේ ම තමන්ගේ මතුල්වහලින් රන්වහලින් ගැ-
- 3 -නුන්පිරිමින්නගෙන් වහල්රුදොස්සයකුන් එලසරකින මිසරකින් සරක්රාසාරසියසකුන්
මෙසේ ම විහාරයෙ කලදොස පවා නොකලදොස කරවා දෙවියන්ට

- 4 මුන්ට නිරනරයෙන් බන්මල්පහන්දූ වලකනන්දූ පවතිනාලෙසට ලංකාවාසි-
සියලුන් තමන්ගේ නම ලා කලහෙයින් අවුරුදුකට ගෙයකින් පනමක් නියාගෙ-
5-න් දොන්ට සලකු පිදොතිපනමුත් ඇතුළුමඩිගයෙන් පිටමඩිගයෙන් නවනොටින්
අවලොස්දොසයෙන් අඩුවපරයන්ගෙන් ගන්නා දො යමබිඳුයෙකින් සියයට
- 6 කාලක් නියායෙන් තඹපන ලියා දුන් සමයභියෙන් ලන් සියළුවකුට ඇතුළුව ඇම-
ලායා පසක් කොට බෙදු තුනුවරුන්ට තුන්භාගයකුන් දෙවියන්ට භාගයකුන් මෙම-
7-තුන්ගේ දරුමුනුබුරුපරපෙරාවෙන් මෙහි පුද පවත්වන කෙනකුන්ට භාගයකුන් නියම
කල නියාවන් මෙසින් කසිමකට විරුඛයක් කොට ලොහයෙන් පැඟවා ගත් කෙ-
8-නෙක් ඇනාමී නරකාදියනරඅපායෙහි ඉපදී මෙතෙමුදුන් නොක්නාහු ය කාකපුනාදීන්
මෙන් බන්පැන් නො ලො වඩාලයන්ටත් අනන ව කඩුබන්ට බලන්ට පුත්
- 9 වුවාහු නම වෙති යි දන ම නිනා වා යදී වා කටයා පුසා වා යදී වා ඵලං ගො හරෙ
බුඹිගොගසා මහාපෙතො හවියයති යි කියා ශ්‍රීමුඛපායභෙයින් මෙලොස්පර-

E

- 1-ලොදෙක්හි ම භෙ විදිනා කැමැතිටු උනමයන් විසින් කසිමකටත් ආයාවක් නො
කොට බසකින් අතුරකින් විවිරකින් මෙපින්කමට සහාය ව කල-
- 2 දොස පවා නොකලදොස පවත්වා කරවා ඒ කෙනෙක් ඇනාමී මෙකුසලය නමන්
කලාසේ අනුමොදව දිවභපන් නිවන්භපන් සාධා ගන්නා පිනිස මෙපි-
- 3-න්කමට සේනාලංකාධිකාරයෝන් මෙසේවූ ආරාධනාවක් කෙරෙන් ම අභය
පුනාසා ය සනානා තන්පැරඛයේ රජ සේනාලංකාධිකාරෙරනපා කුරුනෙ මුළු-
- 4-නි පුසාවන් ම මෙ පින්කමට යම උනමයක්හු විසින් බසකිනවත් සහාය ව
රක්ෂාලොබි ද එඋනමයාගේ පාදවුලි සේනාලංකාධිකාරිටු මා විසින් පුච්චලේ-
- 5-සමුභයක් මෙන් මාගේ ඉසමුදුනෙන් පුදනලදී ම සංරක්ෂිත ධර්මමතොකරුවා
බොධ්දි මුළුති යාවනෝසො භානානරනානාපි භායමානන් මනාභිසාරන් මෙස-
- 6-නාපහාන් බහුශ්‍රී ම සමුදුණේවූ මෙකුසලධර්මය උපන් රාජෙහතමයානානාන්-
සේ විසිනුන් මතු උපදිනා රාජෙහතමයන්විසිනුන් උපන් අමානොත්කමයන් විසි-
- 7-නුන් උපදිනා ඇපාමාපාසිටියෙතෙවිරන්පංචප්‍රධානිමහතුන්විසිනුන් එසේ ම ධනවින-
ශ්‍රීටානදොලසිභලසේනාව විසිනුන් මෙකීපරිදොත් ශ්‍රීමහාවිහාරය සං
- 8-රක්ෂාණවරිපාලනාය කල යම උනමයෙක් ඇනාමී ඔවුන්ට දහනබසමොධානායෝන්
දොසාන් මුදුනෙහි ඇදීලි බැඳ වැදොමී කියා බොධිසන්චරිතයක් මෙන් උතුම -
- 9 වුදුසැඳැනිසේනාලංකාධිකාරිනච්චියන් මෙසේ යාඤ කෙලෙ යි ම දනපාලනායො-
ච්චියා දනා ග්‍රෙයොත්‍රපාලනාම දනා සොභාමුගායොනි පාලනාභයාවුනමි
සේ.

F

1-අම ම යන මේපුභාෂිතවටනායෙන් තමා දීම ය අනුන් දුන් දො රක්ෂාකිරිම-ය
මා පුකතිමුමයෙන් බිඳුවට වපුලුන්ට වඩා වට කොට රක්ෂාකලදොසට එසසාඵලෙස-
මුදොසපන වන සෙයිඤ දරුවන් වැද මැනියන්ට වඩා සුනමුමයෙන් ඇතිකලමුවන්ට
මුදොසගෙන් ප්‍රයොපන වන සෙයිඤ මෙසේ ලංකාසෙනෙවිරන්රජ කරවූ මෙපි-

TRANSCRIPT

A

3-න්කමට වචනමාත්‍රාවකිනවත් සහායවූ කෙනකුන්ට සවර්ගසමපත් නෙචා(ව)නසමපත් සාධා කෙලවර අමාමහනිවන් දක්නාහු නම් වෙන්

ශ්‍රීසහබොධි

4 ශ්‍රීවික්‍රමබාහු නම්වූ මම තුන්වනු උද්වප පුරපසලොස්වක ලත්දිනයෙහි ශවර්ග-මොක්‍ෂසමපත්තිය සාධා ගන්නා පිනිස ලංකාතිලකරජමහාවිහාරයේ නායකපිලිම-

5 සාමීන්ට මාගේ නාමයෙන් දවස්පතා බන් පුදනලෙසට ගොඩරට බඳු පටියෙගම හා මෙහි බදු ගමුදල් ගසකොල වල්පිට මිනිසුන් ඇතුළුව සියලු ම විරාත්කාල-

6-යක් පවත්නාලෙසට මාගෙන් ලොවුතුරාබුදුන්ට පිදුබවටත් ඇපානවර්ෂ මෙවක-වනුදවස මාගෙනුත් රබේගමුව හා මෙහි බදු ගමුදල් ගසකොල වල්පිට මි-

7-නිසුන් ඇතුළුව සියලුන් මට උභයලොකාකීසිසිය පිනිස දෙවියන් බුදුන් සහිත ලංකාතිලකරජමහාවිහාරයට සන්නක කොට මාගෙන් විරාත්කාලයක් පවත්නාලෙස-

8-ට පිදු බවත් මේ අප කලාවූ පින්කමට දන් වන් (න්) ඉදිරියේ දවසකිනවත් අපලක්(ක) කලකීකෙනෙක් ඇත්නම් කොඩාට බලොට පුත්වූබාහු නම් වෙති නිරිසන්ඇසතරඅපා-

-යෙන්-

9 ගොඩ නොදක්නාහු නම් වෙන් මේ අප කලාවූ පින්කමට දන් වන් ඉදිරියේ දවසක වන් මීට බසකින් විවර සහාය ව සිටිකෙනෙක් ඇත්නම් සවර්ගමොක්‍ෂසමපත් සාධා අමා-

G

1 මහනිවන් දකින්නට උත්සාහ කටයුතු

ත්‍රිසිංහලාධිසාර කිණිතිශ්‍රීරාජසිංහ නම්වූ මට එක්විසිවනු පොසොන්මස පුරගටවක ලත් අභහරුවාද පලමු ලංකාතිලක-

2 මහවිහාරයට පුදවා තිබුනු ගොඩවෙල ය යන ගම මා විසින් මෙම විහාරයට පිදුබවටත් ශ්‍රීරාජාධිරාජසිංහ නම්වූ මට සත්වනු ඉල්මස පුරනියවක් නම් නිවේය ලත් සඳුද

3 පලමු ලංකාතිලකමහවිහාරයට පුදවා තිබුනු රබේගමුව යන ගම ගොඩමඩ ගෙවතු ගහකොල පරිවාරජනයන් ඇතුළුව සියලු ම මෙ ම විහාරයට මා විසින් පිදුබවටත්

4 අපට ගුරුතනතුරෙහි සිට අක්‍ෂරලිඛිතාදිසමසනඤායන් අබ්‍යාස කරවමින් ධර්මානුධර්මප්‍රතිපත්තියෙන් අනුශාසනා කරන්නාවූ කොබ්බාසකඩුවේ ශ්‍රීනිවාසසාමීන්ගේ සිඤ්ඤා-

5-නුසිඤ්ඤාපරමපරාව දකවා ශ්‍රීලංකාතිලකමහවිහාරයෙහි පුද වොලකකං පවතී විහාර-සංරක්‍ෂණය කරණ පිනිසත් පලමු භුවණේකකබාහු ආදී මහරාජොත්තමයන් විසින් ග-

6-න්බිම් පමුනු කොට දෙවූසෙසිනුත් මතු ශාසනානන්ධානාස දකවා රාජරාජමහාමාත්‍යාදී කිසිකෙනෙකුන් විසින් නොගතහැකියේ සරීර ව පවත්නානියායෙන් තබපත ලියවා පූජා ක-

7 -ලබවත් දන මින් ඉදිරියේ වන් අපලක් කලකීකෙනෙක් ඇත්නම් සංචිවාදිඅටමහ-නරකයේ වැටී මහදුක් විඳ ගොඩ නොදක්නාහු ය මීට බස්මාත්‍රයකින් වන් සහායවූ

8 කෙනෙක් ඇත්නම් සවර්ගමොක්‍ෂසමපත් සාධා කෙලවර අමාමහනිවන් දක්නාහු නම් වෙති

1 Śri-Śaka-varṣayen ek=vā-dahas-de-siya-sa-śaṭa⁵⁸-avuruddak piru-nu⁵⁹-saṅda me-kala raja pāmīni⁵⁹ T[r*]i-Simhalādhīsvara Bhu-vaṇaikabāhu⁶⁰-nam-vū maṭa tun-

2 vannehi Mehenavara⁵⁹-vaṇśābhijāta Sēnā-Lamkādhikārin=visin Vesaṅga pura-pahalosvaka de-vāsāye maha-saṅghayā - vahansē ek=va Siduruvānā-

3 Uḍunuvara Panahal-gala-mudunehi digin puḷulin śaṭa⁵⁸-śattā⁵⁸-riyanak purṣa⁶¹-pramāna⁵⁹ kaḷu-galin bāṇḍa sama-tala koṭa śai-lamaya-adhiṣṭhāna-mastakāye-

4 -hi noyek-lakṣa-ganan⁵⁹-gadaḷuven satara-mahal koṭa pūrva-disābhimukha⁶²-bappuven yukta koṭa satara-disāvehi candrikā-sthalayen piṭata tān-pasa uḷuven

5 devāla-pasak=ut samaṅga bāṇḍa naṅgana-lada siddha-vidyādhara-hasti-vṛṣabha⁶³-simha-vyāghra-kibisi-makara-pat = ādi-vicitra - kar-mmāntayen samalamkrata⁶³ koṭa vāli-kondehi paṭa-

6 -n kot-kārālla dakvā detis-riyanak bāṇḍa naṅgana-lada satara-konehi⁵⁹ dāgop-satara hā mudun-dāgobehi ran-kot palaṅḍavā mudun-dāgobehi dora-li do-

7 -ra-bā lavā pot-guḷu koṭa piṭakatrāya liyavā tabā sampūrṇṇa-vana-lada-citra-karmmāntayen karavū nāyaka-pilima⁶⁴ - aṭa-vissak hā pilima⁶⁴-sahaśrayakin⁶⁵ sampūrṇṇa

8 sataraveni-māla-t vaḍu-pas-riyan ot-pilima⁶⁴-saminu-t pilima⁶⁴-pasakin=ut sampūrṇṇa va karavū tunveni-mala-t aṭavisi-Bodhiyen =ut sūvisi-vivaraṇāye-

9 -n=ut pilima⁶⁴-sahaśrayakin⁶⁵=ut sampūrṇṇa va muṅḍalivarun āma-denā-t senāva-t ek=va karavū deveni-māla-t tāmbamaya-vū Bodhi-vṛkṣayak⁶³ svarṇṇa-patra-śākhā

B

1 -ven vicitra koṭa karavū Śri-mahābodhi-sāmīnta piṭa lā vajrāsanāye vāḍa hun dhātu-de-siya-pan-śaṭa⁵⁸-denaku-vahansegan dhātu-rūpa-yak pihiṭuvā kala⁶⁴ nāya-

58. Read śa in this word as sā.
59. Read n in this word as ṇ.
60. Read ṇ in this word as n.
61. Read puruṣa.
62. Read s in this word as ś.
63. The subscript ra often stands for medial r in the script of this period.

- 2 -ka-pilima⁶⁴-sāmin=ut ubhaya-pārsvayehi cāmara gena siṭinā vaḍu-
pas-riyan usa divya-rūpa-dekak=ut e-sē ma usa āti Maitrī-nātha
Lokeśvara-nātha rūpa-dekak=ut
- 3 divya-strī-rūpa-dekak=ut karavā sitiyaṃ-pilima⁶⁴-sahaśrayak⁶⁵-
denā-vahansē-t mili-toraṇayehi Śakra-Brahma-Viṣṇu⁵⁹-Mahes-
vara⁶²-Suyāma-Santusit=ādi-vū-divya-rūpa-t meki-āma-de-
- 4 -nā-gē divya-strī-rūpa-t karavā viyan-sittam-bhikti-sittam-dek-hi
pansiya-panas-jātakādin karavā doraṭu-pālayin karavā tabā devāla-
-yehi Lamkāvaṭa arag=gat Kihirā-
- 5 -li⁶⁴-Upulvan-Sumaṇa-Vibhiṣaṇa-Gaṇapati-Khandha-kumār = ādi
devi-rajjuruvan-vahansē-t bisovarun=vahansē-t karavā me-kī Bu-
-dun-deviyangen sampūrṇa-vū Sēnā-Lamkādhikāri
- 6 nam-vū mekun taman karavū pāta-mala-t sthapati-rāyarun ātuḷu-vū
boho-ācārivaruṇṭa dun vīn ratran-ridi-pili-ātulu-vū-deyin masu-
ran-agayen tun-kela⁶⁴-śaṭa⁵⁸-lakṣayak di api-t mu-
- 7 -dalivaru-t sēnāva-t ek=va karavū mē-Śrī-Lamkātilaka-nam-vū
pilima⁶⁶-geyi idiri-piṭa Sēnā-Lamkādhikārayo tamangē putra-
vanitā=diṇ lavā karavū aṭa-ṣi-riyan-mahā-maṇḍapayehi ā-
- 8 -layen makara-tōraṇa-maddhya-gata va pihiṭuvū taman usa-maha-
-taṭa dahas-gaṇan-ghana-lohayen pratimā-rūpayak karavā me-kī
Budun-deviyaṇṭa muḷu-tān piṣimata digin ekolos⁶⁴-riya-
- 9 -n muḷutān-geyak karavā e-maṇḍapa-idiriyehi pūrva-dik-bhāga-
-yehi ek=ṣiya⁶⁶-ṣi-riyan digin puḷulin satara-pas-denakun ovun=
ovun āṅga no-vādi⁶⁷ yana-pariddhen kaḷu-gal-paḍiyak=u-

C

- 1 -t b[ā]ṇḍa yutu-satara-konehi⁵⁹ vaṭa-kaḷu-galin sāra-siyayak-riyan
sīmā-pahurak=ut badavā pascima⁶²-disā⁶²-bhāgayen digin palalin⁶⁷
aṭa-riyan pamana⁵⁹ demāl-maha-vā-
- 2 -salak=ut karavā eyin piṭata vihāra-rakṣāvchi niyukta-dāsi-das-
kam-karuvan innā-lesāṭa vīthi-vinyāsa-t lavā karavā tabā apis-
māḷu-varun-vahanse ātuḷu-
- 3 vū de-vāsaye maha-saṃghayā-vahansē śapa⁵⁸-paribhōgayen śata-
-pena⁵⁸-lesāṭa karavū saṃghārāma-deka-t puṣpārāma-phalārāmayen
yukta-vū śrī-mahā-vihāraya matu pavatvana-

64. Read *l* in this word as *ḷ*.
65. Read *ś* in this word as *s*.
66. Read *ṣ* in this word as *s*.
67. Read *no-vādi*.

- 4 lesāṭa pratisthāvak āta mānavā yi Sēnā-Lamkādhikārayo apaṭa
ki-heyin me-sē ma Siduruvānā-nuvara-bada-Kirivavulen biju-vaṭa-
yālak⁶⁴=ut api-t mudalivaru-t
- 5 sēnāva-t ek=va amutu āla⁶⁴-avunu⁵⁹ baṇḍavā tara karavā ḷu Aḷut-
Badalagoḍin kuṃburu-biju-sa-yālak=ut Paraṇa-Badalagoḍin biju-
pas-yālak=ut ātuḷu va kuṃburu-do-
- 6 -ḷos-yālak⁶⁴=ut mehi bada gasa-kola val-piṭa ātuḷu-vū tān=ut Sēnā-
Lamkādhikārayo tamangē pamunu⁵⁹-pravēniyen⁶⁸ pidū Hidda-
-vulla-Gonmānikayen biju-vaṭa-
- 7 yālak⁶⁴=ut Vāsala-karavū-adhikārayangen⁶⁹ pidū Paraṇa-Badala-
goḍa Yakāllen biju-vaṭa-yālak⁶⁴=ut Satruvan-patirājayangen pidū
Kasabiliyagoḍin biju-vaṭa-yālak⁶⁴=ut
- 8 Āpānangen⁵⁹ pidū Naraṇagoḍin⁷⁰ biju-vaṭa-yālak⁶⁴=ut Patirāja-
-yangen⁷¹ pidū Deltota Silpān-kadure darāṇḍa paṭan Saputalaye
ima dakvā kuṃburu-biju-vaṭa dolo-
- 9 -s=amunak⁵⁹=ut Santānen maṅgul-piṭiyela⁷²-ekak=ut Siduruvānā⁵⁹-
denuvara kuḍā-mahat-āma-dena-t ek=va amutu āla⁶⁴-amunu⁵⁹-
bāṇḍa kanu-mul udurā tanā dunnen pidū Go-

D

- 1 -ḍavelin biju-vaṭa-yālak⁶⁴=ut ātuḷu va kuṃburu-biju-vaṭa -dasasat-
yāla⁶⁴-dolos⁶⁴=amunak⁵⁹ ātuḷu va meyi tuvāk tāna paraṇa-ima-vū-
pariddhen mehi bada gasa-kola
- 2 val-piṭa ātuḷu-vū tān=ut Sēnā-Lamkādhikārayo taman pidū ratran
ridi lo-kaḍa tāmba-kaḍa ātuḷu-vū garu-bhāṇḍa-t mesē ma tamangē
maṅgul-vahalin ran-vahalin gā-
- 3 -nun-pirimingen vahāl-rū-desiyayak=ut ela⁶⁴-sarakin mī-sarakin
sarak-rū-sāra-siyayak=ut mesē ma vihāraye kala⁶⁴-deya pavā⁷³
no-kala⁶⁴-deya karavā deviyaṇṭa
- 4 Buduṇṭa niranatarayen bat-mal-pahan-puda valakkan-puda pava-
tinā-lesāṭa Lamkāvāsi-siyallan tamangē nama lā kala-heyin avurud-
dakāṭa geyakin panamak⁵⁹ niyāye-
- 5 -n denṭa salasanu pideni-panam=ut ātuḷu-maḍigayen piṭa-maḍiga-
-yen nava-totiṇ aṭalos⁶⁴-desayen ā-vāpārayangen gannā dena yam-
baḍuyekin siyayaṭa

68. Read *pravēniyen*.
69. The stone inscription has *Vasa-Lamkā-vari-adhikāra*.
70. The stone has *Nāraṇagoḍin*.
71. The stone has *Jayasīmha-patirājayangen*.
72. The stone has *maḍel-viṭiyala*.
73. Read *pavā*.

- 6 kālak niyāyen taṁba-pata liyā dun samaya-śriyen⁷⁴ lat siyaḷu-vastuva ātuḷu-vū āma-lābhaya pasak koṭa bedā tunu-ruvaṅṅa tun-bhāgayak=ut deviyaṅṅa bhāgayak=ut me-
- 7 -kūṅgē daru-munuburu-paramparāven mehi puda pavatvana kenakuṅṅa bhāgayak=ut niyama kala⁶⁴ niyāva-t meyin kisivakaṭa viruddhayak koṭa lobhayen pāhārā gat ke-
- 8 -nek āt=nam narakādi-satara-apāyehi ipadī Mete-Budun no-daknā-hu ya kāka-pretādin men bat-pān no lāba caṅṅālayaṅṅa-t anta va kavuṅṅaṅṅa ballaṅṅa put
- 9 vūvāhu nam veti yi dāna | Tinam⁵⁹ vā yadi vā kaṅṅam puppam vā yadi vā phalam yo hare Buddha-bhogassa mahāpeto bhavissati yi kiyā śri-mukha-pāṭha heyin mē-lō-para-

E

- 1 lō-dekhi ma śapa⁵⁸ vidinā kāmāti-vū uttamayan visin kisivakaṭa-t āsāvak no koṭa basakin akurakin vicarakin mē-pin-kamaṭa sahāya va kala⁶⁴
- 2 deya pavā⁷³ no-kala⁶⁴-deya pavatvā karavā ḷū kenek āt=nam mē-kusalaya taman kalā⁶⁴-sē anumodan=va diva-śapa-t⁵⁸ nivan-śapa-t⁵⁸ sādha gannā pinisa mē-pi-
- 3 -n-kamaṭa Senā-Lamkādhikarayo-t mesē-vū ārādhanaṅṅa kereti | Aśya punyaśya⁷⁵ yas=trātā tat-pādadvayajam rajah Senā-Lamkādhikārendro⁷⁶ kurute mūrdhva-
- 4 -ni⁷⁷ puṣpa-vat | Mē-pin-kamaṭa yam uttamayakhu visin basakin=va-t sahāya va raknā-lābē da e-uttamayā-gē pāda-dhūli Senā-Lamkādhikārī-vū mā visin suvaṅṅa-mal-
- 5 samūhayak men māgē isa-mudunen pudana-ladī | Samrakṣitum dharmmam = anaikarūpaṁ⁷⁸ baddhāñjali⁷⁹ mūrdhvani⁸⁰ yācate 'sau jātā-narendrān=napi⁸¹ jayamānān mantrisvarān⁶² sai-
- 6 -nya-janān bahuśri⁸² | sampūrṅṅa-vū mē-kusala⁶²-dharmmaya upan rājottamayānan⁸³=vahansē visin=ut matu upadinā rājottama-yan=visin=ut upan amāptottamayan⁸⁴ visi-

74. Read *samayaśrayen* ?
 75. Read *Aśya punyasya*.
 76. Read *Senā-Lamkādhikarendraḥ*.
 77. Read *mūrdhni*.
 78. Read *aneka-rūpaṁ*.
 79. Read *baddhāñjalir*.
 80. Read *mūrdhni*.
 81. Read *jātān=narendrān=api*.
 82. Read *bahuśrīḥ*.
 83. Read *rājottamayānan*.
 84. Read *amāptottamayan*.

- 7 -n=ut upadinā āpā-māpā-siṭu-senevirat-paṅca-pradhāni-mahatun=visin=ut esē ma dhanavanta-śrīvanta - Demala⁶⁴ - Sihala-sēnāva visin=ut me-kī-pariddhen śri-mahā-vihāraya sarin-
- 8 rakṣaṅṅa-paripālanaya kala⁶⁴ yam uttamayek āt=nam ovuṅṅa dasa-nakha-samodhānayen dohot mudunehi ādili bāṅṅa vāndemi kiyā Bodhisatva-caritayak men utum-
- 9 vū-guna-āti-cē-Senā-Lamkādhikārīn=visin mesē yājñā⁸⁵ keḷe⁶⁴ yi | Dāna-pālanayorm=madhe⁸⁶ dānā śreyo⁸⁷ 'nupālanam dānaṁ svarg-gam=prāpnoti⁸⁸ pālanaśyācutam⁸⁹

F

- 1 padam | yana mē-subhāsita-vacanayen tamā dīma ya anun dun deya rakṣā-kirīma ya yana yukti-kramayen biju-vaṭa vapulavunṅa⁶⁴ vaḍā v[ä*]ṭa koṭa rakṣā-kala⁶⁴-ayaṭa e-sasya⁶²-phalaye-
- 2 -n prayojana vana seyin=da daruvan vāda māniyaṅṅa vaḍā suta-premayen āti-kala⁶⁴-mavunṅa cē-put[r*]ayāgen prayojana vana śeyin⁵⁵=da me-sē Lamkā-Senevirat-raja karavū mē-pi-
- 3 -n-kamaṭa vacana-mātrāvakin=vat sahāya-vū kenakuṅṅa svargga-sampat nervā(va)na-sampat⁹⁰ sādha kelavara⁶⁴ amā-maha-nivan daknāhu nam vet ||

Śri-Saṅgabodhi

- 4 Śri-Vikramabāhu nam-vū mama tun=vanu Uduvapa purapaslosvaka⁶⁴ lat-dinayehi svargga-mokṣa-sampattiya sādha gannā-pinisa⁵⁹ Lamkātilaka-raja-mahā-vihāraye nāyaka-pilima⁶⁴-
- 5 sāmīṅṅa māgē nāmāyēn dāvas-patā bat pudana-lesāṭa Goḍaraṭa baṅṅa Paṭṭiyegama hā mehi bada gam=mudal gasa-kola⁶⁴ val-piṭa minisun ātuḷu-vū siyalla ma cirāt-kāla-
- 6 -yak pavatnā-lesāṭa māgen Lovuturā-Budunṅa pidū-bavaṭat | Āpāna⁵⁹ vamha [r*] Me-vakavanu-davasa māgen=ut Rabbēgamuva hā mehi bada gam = mudal gasa-kola val-piṭa mi-
- 7 -nisun ātuḷu-vū siyalla-t maṭa ubhaya-lokārṭṭha-sidhiya pinisa⁵⁹ deviyaṅṅa Budun sahita Lamkātilaka-raja-mahā-vihārayaṅṅa santaka koṭa māgen cirāt-kālayak pavatnā-lesa-

85. Read *yācñā*.
 86. Read *madhye*.
 87. Read *dānāt=chreyo*.
 88. Read *dānāt svarggam=avāpnoti*.
 89. Read *pālānād=acyutam*.
 90. Read *Nirvāṅṅa*.

- 8 -ta pidū bava-t mē apa kalā⁶⁴-vū pin-kamaṭa dān vat (t) idiriye davasakin=vat apalak⁹¹(ka) kala=⁶⁴ki-kenek āt=nam kauḍāta⁹² ballāṭa put-vūvāhu nam veti tirisana-ā-satara-apāyen
- 9 goḍa no-daknāhu nam vet mē apa kalā-vū pin-kamaṭa dān vat idiriye davasaka vat mīṭa basakin vicara sahāya va siṭi-kenek āt=nam svargga-mokṣa sampat sādha amā-

G

- 1 maha-nivan dakinta utsāha kaṭa yutu |
Tri-Simhalādhisvara⁹³ Kīrtti-Srī-Rājasimha nam-vū maṭa ek-
-visi-vanu Posa-masa pura-śaṭa⁵⁸-vaka lat Aṅgaharuvā-dā palamu⁶⁴
Lankātilaka-
- 2 maha-vihārayaṭa pudavā tibunu⁵⁹ Goḍavela ya yana gama mā
visin me ma vihārayaṭa pidū-bavaṭa-t |
Śrī-Rājādhiraśasimha nam-vū maṭa sat-vanu Il-masa pura-
-tiyavak nam tithiya lat Saṅdu-dā
- 3 palamu⁶⁴ Lankātilaka-maha-vihārayaṭa pudavā tibunu⁵⁹ Rabbē
gamuva yana gama goḍa maḍa ge-vatu gaha-kola⁶⁴ parivāra-
janayan ātuḷu-vū siyalla ma me ma vihārayaṭa mā visin pidū-bavaṭa-t
- 4 apaṭa guru-tanaturehi siṭa akṣara-likhit=ādi-samasta-śāstrayan ab-
-bhyāsa karavamin dhammānu-dharmma⁹⁴-pratipattiyen anuśā-
-sanā karannā-vū Kobbyākaḍuvē⁹⁵ Śrīnivāsa-sāmin-gē siśyā-
-nu-siśya⁹⁶-paramparāva dakvā Śrī-Lankātilaka-maha-vihārayeḥi
puda volakkam pavatvā vihāra-saṁrakṣaṇaya karaṇa⁶⁰ pinisa⁵⁹-t |
Palamu⁶⁴ Bhuvanāikabāhu-ādi-maha-rājottamayan visin ga-
-n⁹⁷-bim pamunu⁵⁹ koṭa devū-seyin=ut matu śāsanāntarddhānaya
dakvā rāja-rājamahāmāptyādi⁹⁸-kisi-kenakun visin no-gata-hāki-ś
sthira va pavatnā-niyāyen taṁba-pata liyavā pūjā ka-
-la⁶⁴-bava-t dāna | Min idiriye vat apalak kala⁶⁴-ki-kenek āt=nam
Saṅjivādi-āṭa-maha-narakaye vāṭi maha-duk viṇḍa goḍa no dak-
nāhu ya | Mīṭa bas-mātrayakin vat sahāya-vū
- 8 kenek āt=nam svargga-mokṣa-sampat sādha kelavara⁶⁴ amā
maha-Nivan daknāhu nam veti |||

91. The stone inscription has *avulak*.
92. Read *kavudāṭa*.
93. Read *°śvara*.
94. Read *dharmmā=nu-dharmma*.
95. Read *Kobbākaḍuve*.
96. Read *siśyā=nu-siśya*.
97. Read *gan*.
98. Read *mahā=mātyādi*.

TRANSLATION

[Ll. A1-A2]. When One Thousand Two Hundred and Sixty-six years had been completed in the era of the illustrious Śaka (king)—on the fifteenth of the bright half of Vesaṅga⁹⁹ in the third year of me, named Bhuvanaika-bāhu, who has attained to the sovereignty at this time. By Senā-Lankādhikarin born in the Meheṇavara family.

[Ll. A2-B7]. The two Venerable Communities¹⁰⁰ of the eminent Saṅgha in unison caused to be prepared, by making it level, an area sixty and seventy cubits in length and breadth, (respectively), by retaining¹⁰¹ (it) with granite to the height of a man,¹⁰² and on the stone base (*adhiṣṭhāna*) thus formed, (caused to be constructed) with many hundreds of thousands of bricks, (a shrine) of four storeys provided with a porch¹⁰³ facing the eastern direction, and having constructed of brick five shrines for gods (*devāla*) at five places outside the moonlight terraces,¹⁰⁴ adorned (that shrine) with ornamental work such as (figures) in relief¹⁰⁵ of *siddhas*, *vidyādhara*s, elephants, bulls, lions, tigers, *kibisi*,¹⁰⁶ *makara-pat*,¹⁰⁷ etc., placed golden pinnacles on the four *dāgābas* at the four corners and on the *dāgāba* on the summit, which was built so as to have an elevation of thirty-two cubits from the base-moulding (of the shrine) up to the pinnacle (of the *dāgāba*), provided a library inside the uppermost *dāgāba*, constructing (a chamber) with door-frames and lintels, caused the Tripiṭaka to be transcribed and deposited in that chamber. (The shrine comprised) the fourth storey complete with twenty-eight principal images and a thousand other images (all) executed in painting, the third storey complete with Its Lordship the Recumbent Image, seven carpenters' cubits in length, and five other images, the second storey complete with the twenty-eight Trees of Wisdom, the Twenty-four Predictions¹⁰⁸ and a thousand images, which (storey) was caused to be constructed by all the chiefs (*mudali*) and the host together, and the lowermost storey, caused to be constructed by this personage named Senā-Lankādhikari himself, housing Its Lordship the Principal Image, made by

99. See above, note 15.
100. See above, note 18.
101. *Bānda*, lit. 'tied.'
102. Lit., 'the proportions of a man.'
103. *Bappuven*. This architectural term does not appear to occur elsewhere. It is derived from Tamil *parappu* 'extension.'
104. *Candrikā-sthala*.
105. *Nagana-lada*, 'raised.'
106. *Kibisi-mūna* is the Sinhalese term for the ornament called *kīrtimukha* in Indian architecture.
107. The significance of *-pat* after *makara* is not clear.
108. See above, note 19.

installing therein a relic-image with Their Lordships of two hundred and fifty-two relics—which Image) is seated on the Diamond Throne with back to Its Lordship the Illustrious Great Bodhi-tree beautified with branches and leaves of gold on a Bodhi-tree¹⁰⁹ of copper—and on either side (of the principal Image) two images of gods each five carpenter's cubits in height, standing with *cāmaras* in their hands, (and moreover) two images of Lord Maitrī and Lord Lokeśvara of similar height, two images of celestial damsels, their lordships of a thousand painted images, the celestial forms of Śakra, Brahma, Viṣṇu, Mahesvara, Suyāma, Santusita and others, and the forms of the celestial damsels of all the beings aforesaid—all of these executed on the (*makara*)-*torana* of *mī* wood, (which storey) also contained (representations) of the five hundred and fifty Jātakas and other (subjects), both among the paintings on the ceiling and the paintings on the walls (and was completed) by having made and installed (the figures of) the guardians of the gate and in the shrines of the gods the images of Their Lordships Kihirāḷi-Upulvan who has assumed (the task of) the protection of Laṅkā, Sumaṇa, Vibhīṣana Gaṇapati, Khandhakumāra and others, together with images of their divine consorts—the lowermost storey (thus) complete with the images of Buddha and gods enumerated above.

[Ll. B7-C4]. In front of this image-house named Laṅkātilaka which we (Bhuvanaikabāhu), the chiefs (*mudali*) and the hosts in unison caused to be built by spending a sum of thirty-six millions in *masuran* reckoning including paddy, gold, silver, cloths and other payments in kind, made to numerous artisans including Sthapatirāyara, Senā-Laṅkādhikāra caused to be erected by his sons, ladies of his household and others, a great *mandapa* twenty-eight cubits (in length), and on one side¹¹⁰ of this (*mandapa*) was installed an image (of the Buddha) within a *makara-torana*, made of solid bronze, weighing thousands,¹¹¹ and equivalent in height and breadth to his own stature. (He) also constructed a kitchen, eleven cubits in length, for cooking offerings of food to the Buddha and the deities above mentioned. To the east, facing the said *mandapa*, he also caused to be constructed a flight of steps one hundred and twenty cubits in length, and of a breadth sufficient for four or five persons to go along abreast without touching each other's body.

He also constructed a boundary wall of granite four hundred cubits (in perimeter) with at the four corners.¹¹² On the western side

109. The trunk of the Bodhi-tree is meant.

110. *Ālayen*.

111. The unit of the measurement of weight is not given; the *kalaṅḍa* was probably meant.

112. *Yutu satara koṇehi*: A word or words appear to have been omitted here.

built a great gateway of two storeys, measuring eight cubits in length as well as its breadth, outside which he laid out streets for those engaged in the service of the *vihāra*,¹¹³ including male slaves, female slaves, workmen and others, to reside in. He also established two convents for the comfortable lodging of the venerable members of the Saṅgha of the two fraternities, including senior *theras* of moderate wants, flower-gardens and orchards of fruit trees. And whereas Senā-Laṅkādhikāra intimated to us that an endowment should be made for the maintenance of this (shrine) in the future (the following grants have been made):¹¹⁴

[Ll. E4-F3]. 'Should there be any noble persons who would protect and preserve in the said manner this complete act of religious merit, namely the illustrious great *vihāra*, be it a pre-eminent king already born (i.e. now living) or a pre-eminent king to be born in the future, or a pre-eminent minister already born (i.e. now living), or great dignitaries such as princes, nobles, bankers, generals, heads of castes,¹¹⁵ or likewise the illustrious and wealthy members of the army, Tamil as well as Sinhalese, I salute them with my two hands, with the ten finger-nails close together, placed on my head.' So saying, that great Senā-Laṅkādhikāri, bearing noble virtues like unto the conduct of a Bodhisattva, made this exhortation.

Between giving and the protection of what has been given, protection is the more meritorious. By giving one attains Heaven; by protection, Immortality'. According to this well-said adage, the argument with regard to the relative benefits of one-self giving and protecting what has been given by others is analogous to that a person who guards a field by having a fence derives greater benefit from the harvest than the one who has merely sown the seed, and that a mother who has brought up a child with the affection due to a son obtains greater benefits from that son than the mother who had only given birth to a son. In this wise, any persons who sustain the act of religious merit effected by the king Laṅkā-Senevirat will obtain for themselves happiness in Heaven and the happiness of Nivāṇa; in the end they will realise for themselves the Great Nirvāṇa which is Immortality.

113. *Vihāra-rakṣāvehi*: See *Ep. Zey.*, Vol. IV, p. 259. n. 6.

114. For the translation of the text C4—E4, see the translation of the rock inscription, II. 12-33.

115. *Āpā, māpā, siṭu, senevirat, pañca-pradhāna*. For these various dignitaries, see *University History of Ceylon*, Vol. I, pp. 365ff., 538ff. and 732f.

116. Here (11. F4—G1) follows the inscription of Vikramabāhu III, for the translation of which, see above, p. 16.

[Ll. G1-2]. To the effect that the village of Goḍavela which had formerly been dedicated to the great *vihāra* of Laṅkātilaka has been dedicated (again) to this self-same *vihāra* by me on Tuesday, the sixth day of the waxing moon in the month of Poson in the twenty-first year of me,¹¹⁷ by name Kīrtti-Śrī-Rājasimha, the Lord of the Three Siṃhalas, (this has been written).

[Ll. G2-G8]. To the effect that the village of Rabbegamu, which had been dedicated formerly to the Laṅkātilaka-*vihāra*, including high lands and mud lands, house-sites, trees, men attached (to it) and all else, was dedicated (again) to the self-same *vihāra* by me on Monday, bearing the third *tithi* of the waxing moon in the month of Il in the seventh (year) of me,¹¹⁸ named Śrī-Rājādhirājasimha, for the purpose of maintaining the *vihāra*, conducting offerings and audiences in this great *vihāra* of Laṅkātilaka up to (the end of) the pupillary succession of His Reverence Kobbākaḍuve Śrīnivāsa who, occupying the position of teacher to us, advises us with regard to conduct according to the religion, also making us proficient in all branches of learning such as letters and writing—(this has been written).

Know¹¹⁹ therefore that estates and lands have been granted as freehold formerly by great and eminent kings beginning with Bhuvanaikabāhu, and that this dedication has been made having had it written on copper-plates, so that it may not be confiscated in the future by kings, great ministers of kings, and others up to the disappearance of the Śāsana. Should there be any persons hereafter who will cause any obstacle to this, they will fall into the eight great hells of which the first is Sañjīva, and suffer great torment there, and will not see deliverance therefrom. On the other hand, should there be any persons who will support this by a mere word even, they will obtain the affluence of Heaven and Liberation, and will in the end see the Great Nirvāṇa which is Immortality.

VI. ALAVALA-AMUNA ROCK INSCRIPTION

The Sinhalese, as well as the Tamil, inscription at the Laṅkātilaka temple registers the grant of extensive fields at Badalagoḍa to that shrine. This grant has also been recorded in an epigraph sited close to the lands affected, so that the local people concerned, particularly the tenants, may be made aware of the fact. This is the inscription engraved in large and

117. Tuesday, 2nd June, 1767 A.C.

118. Monday, 12th November, 1787 A.C.

119. Literally, 'having known therefore that,' etc.

clear characters on a rock by the side of the stream known as Kospotu Oya, close to the dam at Alavaḷa in the Hēvāvisse Kōraḷē of the Kuruṇāgala District.

The inscription is No. 171 in E. Müller's *Ancient Inscriptions in Ceylon*. But that scholar has given neither the text nor the translation of the record. He does not appear to have made an attempt to read the record, either ; but has merely repeated what the villagers told him of it. For he says : 'Alavala Amuna at Kospotu Oya anicut, about six miles from Kurunaegala ; there is a long inscription on a rock close to the river. It contains a grant to the temple of Maedagama, which is situated in the neighbourhood, by King Parākramabāhu of Dambadeniya.'¹²⁰ This is what I was also told by the people of the place when I visited the site in 1931 to copy the inscription. As the subjoined text and translation of the record would testify, the grant registered in the document was not to the benefit of the Mādagoḍa temple. As the inscription refers to the building of the Laṅkātilaka temple, and mentions Senā-Laṅkā-adhikāra in this connection, the king referred to cannot be Parākramabāhu of Daṁbadeṇi.

But this belief of the people of the place could possibly have been due to the mention of a king named Parākramabāhu in the inscription. The first ten lines of the record have been badly damaged, obviously due to a wilful attempt by treasure-seekers, and the king's name, which was in the fourth line, has been lost for ever. As the document registers grants made to the then newly founded temple of Laṅkātilaka, the royal donor must be Bhuvanaikabāhu IV or Parākramabāhu V, of whom the latter's reign for the most part coincided with that of the former. Müller does not mention that the first ten lines of the record were damaged when he inspected it ; possibly he could read the name of Parākramabāhu in line 4, and was therefore inclined to accept without hesitation the opinion of the villagers recorded above. As will be shown later, there is reason to conclude that the rock-inscription at Alavaḷa-amuna was published some years after the engraving of the inscriptions at Laṅkātilaka.

H. W. Codrington, in his paper on Gāvuta Pillars, has referred to this inscription and has quoted a sentence from it¹²¹; in fact, he appears to have been the first to appreciate the real historical significance of the record. As referred to earlier, I visited the site in 1931, and an excellent estampage of the record was prepared under my direction by Mr. T. K. Jayasundara.

120. E. Müller, *AIC.*, p. 72.

121. *CJSG.*, Vol. II, p. 133.

I also read the inscription directly from the stone. It has been numbered 668 in the Inscriptions Register of the Archaeological Department, and a brief reference has been made to it in the 'Epigraphical Summary' in the *Ceylon Journal of Science, Section G, Vol. II, part 3*.¹²²

The inscription covers an area of 12 ft. by 11 ft. 8 in., and consists of thirty-three lines. The letters, which are deeply and clearly engraved, vary in size between $2\frac{3}{4}$ in. and $5\frac{1}{4}$ in. The script, on the whole, is the same as in other records of the middle of the fourteenth century, e.g. the Gaḍalādeṇi rock-inscription of Dharmakīrti-sthavira.¹²³ The language, when compared with that of the Laṅkātilaka inscription, favours archaic forms. Instead of *mudali-varun* in the Laṅkātilaka inscription, this record has *pradhāna-gaṇā*. We also come across herein the conjunction *isā*, so common in documents of the tenth century. In fact, so far as is known, the word has been used for the last time in this document.

This record does not go into so much of details about the founding of the Laṅkātilaka temple as does the inscription engraved by the side of the shrine. But, as is to be expected, it gives more details about the opening up of fields under the Batalagoḍa-vāva, and enumerates the lands donated from that area in greater detail. The other grants to the Laṅkātilaka temple are referred to only in a general way. A point worthy of note is that, according to the Laṅkātilaka inscriptions, fields granted to that temple from Badalagoḍa, Old and New, Kasambīliyagoḍa and Nāramgoḍa were of a total extent of fourteen *yālas*, whereas according to the present document, ninety *yālas* of fields were granted to the temple from these four villages. If so much of land had been granted to the temple when the Laṅkātilaka inscription was being indited, there is no reason for that document to have recorded a much lesser extent. The probability is that, after the publication of the inscriptions on the site of the temple, more lands were brought under the plough below the Batalagoḍa tank, and the income from these fields was also dedicated to the Laṅkātilaka temple. This circumstance would lead one to the conclusion that the record at Alavaḷa-amaṇa was some years later in date than that at Laṅkātilaka. The king mentioned in the present epigraph could therefore have been Parākrama-bāhu V.

The imprecations and exhortations at the end are also given in brief, there being only one Sanskrit stanza instead of the two in the Laṅkātilaka

Laṅkātilaka : I. Inscription of Bhuvanaikabāhu IV.
II. Inscription of Vikramabāhu III.

122. *Ibid.*, pp. 188 and 213.
123. *Ep. Zey.*, Vol. IV, pp. 90-110 ; Plate 10.

Laṅkātilaka: Tamil Inscription

LANKATILAKA INSCRIPTIONS

Inscription. The contents of the Sanskrit verse are not repeated in Sinhalese. The phrase *anūnam=chāmi* in the Sanskrit verse in place of *anāka-rūpam* in the Lankatilaka inscription is decidedly an improvement.

TEXT

- 1
- 2 පැමිණි ණී
- 3 ශ්‍රීජනන[වා]නු[ඤා]
- 4 සශ්‍රීකවු සුයඹව
- 5 ස්වාමීන්වහන්සේට
- 6 නම මැනීමුමා තමා මතු බුදු වන්ට
- 7 උභයවාසයෙහි මහසංඝයාවහන්සේ කරවු චිහාරයෙ[හි]
- 8 ලෝකගායනාරක්ෂාවෙහි දක්ෂවු රජුරැඤාමීන් බියො
- 9 තුන්වැනිමාලෙහි නායකඤාමීන් ඇතුළුවු පිළිමලහස සෙනා-
- 10 -වන් ප්‍රධානගණන් එක් වැ කරවු අවච්ඡිඛොධියෙන් සන්
- 11 සමුච්චි දෙව-
- 12 -නමාලෙහි පිළිමදසක් ඉසා තුන්රජයේ සෙනාවෙන් පිහිට ලන් සෙනාලංකාඅධිකාර-
- 13 -යන් කරවු පළමුවැනිමාලෙහි වජ්‍රාසනයෙ යාමීන් පන්සියසතස්ඡාතකය පිළිම-
- 14 -දස-
- 15 -ත් ඇතුළු වැ පිළිමපන්දසකින් සලෝචිතවු බ්‍රහ්මවිෂ්ණුමහෙසේරසනරවරමානිහිරළි-
- 16 උපුල්වන්සමන්විභීෂණගණපතිකඤ්ඤාමාරආදීලෝකපාලදෙවියන්ගෙහුන් බ-
- 17 -බළන්තාවු ලංකාතිලකය රන්තූන්කෙළසැටලක්ෂයක් දී කරවා උභයවාසයෙ
- 18 -සංඝාර-
- 19 -ම කරවා මතු පවත්නාලෙස භූමීදායක් ඇත මැනවැ යි සිතා වදාරා යම යම කෙනතුන්
- 20 සාතක ගමක් බිමක් උදුරා පිදුවොත් මතු නො පවති කියා ප්‍රධානගණ හා සෙනාව
- 21 -ර-
- 22 ගෙන රජුරැඤාමී මෙම කෙනට වැඩැ වදාරා අමුතුව ඇළඅමුණු බඳවා වෙල් වල් ක-
- 23 -ඵසා තන ගොවීන් එඩේරන් වහල් සරක් පුද මතු ඇතිවන රජුරවරජමහාඅමාත්‍යාදීන්-
- 24 -ගෙන් නුභූඵවනලෙස ඉරසඤ්ඤමපමුණු කොට පුද වදාළ පරණබදලගොඩ
- 25 කසබේළියගොඩ නාරම්ගොඩ අලුත්බදලගොඩ ඇතුළුවුගමසතරින් ස-
- 26 -කරදිඛින් යොන්තකින් කුඹුරුබිජුවටඅනුයාළක් ඉසා සිඟුරැචාණෙන් සිද්දල්ලේ
- 27 ගොන්වණකේ කිරිවවුලට ගොඩවෙල ඇතුළුවුකෙනින් කුඹුරුබිජුවට තුන්යාළක්
- 28 -ඉසා
- 29 සැදූඇත්තන්ගෙන් නොඑක්කෙන පිදු කුඹුරුබිජුවටසන්යාළක් ඇතුළු ව කුඹුරුබි-
- 30 -ජුවටසියක්යාළන් මෙහි තුවක් කෙනට හයකින් වන්කෙනතුන්ට අභයදානන්
- 31 දෙවා වදාරා මෙයින් ලන් යම ම දෙයක් තුනුවන්ට තුන්හාගයන් සලස්වා මේ-
- 32 -දොවලසට හාගසක් චිහාරය මතු පවත්වන සෙනාලංකාඅධිකාරනමානෙහිහුගෙ
- 33 බන්වුන්ට හාගසෙකැ යි පසක් නියාවට බෙද දෙවා වදාරා මීට අනිකක් කී කළ එ-
- 34 -කෙක් පන්වමණ්ඩාලයන්ටත් අන්ත ව කවුඩන්ටත් බල්ලන්ටත් [වු]න් වෙයි තරකා-

- 30 -දියන් [ඉ*]නමේ ම දක්කි බසකිනුත් සහයවූ උන්තමයෙක් මෙයින් කුසල්භාග-
 31 -යක් ලැබ දිවසැපත් නිවන්සැපත් ලැබෙයි වදරා මෙතැන්හි මැ වැඩැ සිටැ ලියවැ
 වදළ
 32 ඉසා [[*] සංරක්ෂිතං ධර්මමනුනමෙනම් බඩාක්ෂ්ලිමුධරීති යාවනෙ'සො[[*]
 33 ජානාන් නරෙත්‍රානපි ජායමානාන් මනත්‍රිවෙරානනාජනාන් බහුත්‍රි[*][*]
 ශ්‍රමසු [[*]

TRANSCRIPT

- 1
 2 pāmiṇi Tri
 3 Śri-Danta-dhātu-s[vā]
 4 sa-śrika-vū sūryya-va
 5 svāmin-vahansēṭa
 6 nam māti-tumā tamā matu Budu vaṇṭa
 7 ubhaya-vāsayehi maha-saṅghayā-vahansē karavū vihāraye[hi] ..
 8 loka-śāsana-rakṣāvehi dakṣa-vū rajjuru-svāmīn biso
 9 tun-vāni-mālchi nāyaka-svāmīn ātuḷu-vū piḷima-dahasā
 senā-
 10 -va-t pradhāna-gaṇā-t ek vā kāravū aṭa-visi-Bodhiyen sat
 samurddha¹²⁴-vū deva-
 11 -na-mālehi piḷima-dāsak isā tun-rajayē senāven pihiṭa lat Senā-
 Laṅkā-adhikāra-
 12 -yan kāravū paḷamu-vāni-mālehi vajrā=sanaye sāmīn pansiya-
 panas-jātakaya piḷima-de-dāsa-
 13 -k ātuḷu vā piḷima-pan-dāsakin samanvita-vū Brahma-Viṣṇu-
 Maheśvara-Satara-varam-Kihirāḷi-
 14 Upulvan-Saman-Vibhīṣaṇa-Gaṇapati -Kandakumāra-ādi-loka-pāla
 deviyangen=ut ba
 15 -baḷannā-yū Laṅkātilakaya ran-tun-keḷa-sāṭa-lakṣayak dī karavā
 ubhaya-vāsaye saṅghārā-
 16 -ma karavā matu pavatnā-lesa bhūmi-dānayaḷ āta mānavā yī
 sitā vadārā yam yam kenakun
 17 santaka gamak bimak udurā piduvot matu no pavatī kiyā pradhā-
 -na-gaṇā hā senāva ara-
 18 gena rajjuru-sāmī me ma tenaṭa vāḍā vadārā amutu va āḷa-amuṇu
 bandavavā vel val ka-
 19 -ppā tana govīn eḍēran vahal sarak pudā matu āti vana raja-
 yuvarāja-mahā-amātyādin-

124. Read *samrddha*.

- 20 -gen nūguḷuvana-lesa ira-sanda-im-pamuṇu koṭa pudā vadāḷa
 Parana-Badalagoḍa
 21 Kasambīḷiyagoda Nāramgoḍa Alut-Badalagoḍa ātuḷu-vū-gam-
 satarin sa-
 22 -tara-digin yotnakin kuṁburu-biju-vaṭa-anū-yāḷak isā Siṅguru-
 vānen Siddāulla
 23 Gonvaṇakē Kirivavuluva Goḍavela ātuḷu-vū-tenin kuṁburu-
 biju-vaṭa-tun-yāḷak isā
 24 sādā-āttangen no-ek-tena pidū kumburu-biju-vaṭa sat-yāḷak
 ātuḷu va kumburu-bi-
 25 -ju-vaṭa siyak-yāḷa-t mehi tuvak tenaṭa bhayakin van kenakunṭa
 abhaya-dāna-t
 26 devā vadārā meyin lat yam ma deyak tunu-ruvaṇṭa tun-bhāgaya-t
 salasvā mē-
 27 devāla-pasaṭa bhāgayak vihāraya matu pavatvana Senā-Laṅkā-
 adhikāra-nam-mantriḷu-ge
 28 bandhūṇṭa bhāgayekā yī pasak niyāvaṭa bedā devā vadārā miṭa
 anikak ki kaḷa e-
 29 -kek panca-caṇḍālayaṇṭa-t anta va kavuḍaṇṭa ballaṇṭa-t p[u*]t veyi
 narakā-
 30 -diyāt tamē ma¹²⁵ dakki basakin=ut sahaya-vū uttamayek meyin
 kusāl-bhāga-
 31 -yak lāba diva-sāpat nivan-sāpat lābe yī vadārā me-tānhi mā vāḍā
 sitā liyavā vadāḷa
 32 isā[*] Saṁrakṣitum dharmmam=anūnam=enam baddhāñjalir=
 mūrddhvanī¹²⁶ yācate 'sau [[*]
 33 jātān narendrān=api jāyamānān mantri=śvarān=anya janān bahu-
 śrī[h*] [[*] Śubham=astu[[*].

TRANSLATION

[Ll. 1-15]. the Illustrious who has
 attained Lordship the Tooth Relic¹²⁷ the
 Solar Race which is full of splendour unto His Majesty
 the Minister named in order that he may become a Buddha
 in the future in the monastery caused to be established by
 the two Venerable Communities of the eminent Saṅgha
 His Majesty the King skilled in protecting the world and the religion, and

125. Read *temē ma*.
 126. Read *mūrddhani*.
 127. Perhaps the mention of the Tooth-Relic is in connection with the origin of the family of
 which the king was a scion.

the Queen a thousand images including Its Lordship the Principal (Image) in the third storey and a thousand images in the second storey which was made resplendent with (representations of the twenty-eight Trees of Wisdom and the Seven and in the first storey caused to be built by Senā-Laṅkā-adhikāra who has also received assistance therefor from the army of the Three Kingdoms, were installed The Lord on the Diamond Throne, five thousand images¹²⁸ including two thousand images depicting the five hundred and fifty Jātakas together with figures of gods, the protectors of the world such as Brahmā, Viṣṇu Maheśvara, the Four Varam (Mahārājas), Kihirāli-Upulvan, Saman, Vibhiṣaṇa, Gaṇapati and Kandakumāra.

[Ll. 15-25]. Having built the Laṅkātilaka shrine resplendent with (the above) by spending thirty-six millions, and having established convent for the two confraternities, (His Majesty) thought that it would be appropriate if there be a grant of land for its maintenance in the future. (His Majesty further) reflected that such grant will not endure in the future if the dedication be made by expropriating an estate or a piece of land belonging to someone else. His Majesty the King (therefore) came to this spot, taking with him the company of chiefs¹²⁹ and the army, constructed channels and dams anew, prepared fields having forests felled down, dedicated farmers, herdsmen, slaves and cattle and granted (these) so that they may not be confiscated by any king, sub-king or great ministers that may arise in the future, constituting into a free-hold (*pamuṇu*) to endure as long as the sun and the moon, fields of a sowing extent of ninety *yālas* of seed (paddy) within an area of a *yotma*¹³⁰ in the four directions and situated in the four villages of Paraṇa Badalagoḍa, Kasambiḷiyagoḍa, Nāramgoḍa and Alut Badalagoḍa, fields of a sowing extent of three *yālas* of seed paddy from places including Siddāulla, Gonvaṇakē, Kirivavuluva and Goḍavela in Siṅgurutvāṇa and fields of a sowing extent of seven *yālas* of seed paddy granted from various places by pious persons—comprising (in all) fields up to a sowing extent of a hundred *yālas* of seed paddy.

[Ll. 25-33]. (His Majesty further) granted the right of sanctuary to any person coming to any of the said lands through fear; (His Majesty) divided any income obtained from these lands into five shares, apportioning

three shares therefrom to the Three Jewels (Buddha, Dhamma and the Saṅgha), one share to these five *devālas* and one share to kinsmen of the minister Senā-Laṅkā-adhikāra who would administer the *vihāra* in the future.

One who might say or do anything contrary to this (charity) will be even meaner than the five *caṇḍāla* (castes) and become a son unto crows and dogs; he will see for himself (the four evil existences of which) the first (is) Hell. Any great one who would support this even by a word will obtain a share of this merit, and obtain for himself the happiness of Heaven and the happiness of Nirvāṇa. Having vouchsafed thus, His Majesty came and stood at this very spot and had this written.

He of varied splendour with fingers clasped upon his head beseeches kings who are already born, kings who will be born in the future and likewise great ministers and other people, to protect this charity undiminished. May there be welfare.

S. PARANAVITANA

128. The inscription at Laṅkātilaka refers to three thousand images only on the ground floor of the temple.

129. *Pradhāna-gaṇā*.

130. Skt. *yojana*, See CJS.G., Vol. II, p. 132.